

A Partial Theory Of Everything And The Hierarchy Of Life In The Universe

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Important To Point Out

You can speak of the structure of the solar system even though it changes with time. This is important to understand when I refer to sizes of the Moon and the planets, and their orbital distances.

The whole object of developing a theory for the way planetary systems form is that they meet the following criterion: They predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of the planets; the distribution gives the planetary orbital periods from Newton's Universal Law of Gravitation. The distribution of the planets is chiefly predicted by three factors: The inward forces of gravity from the parent star, the outward pressure gradient from the stellar production of radiation, and the outward inertial forces as a cloud collapses into a flat disc around the central star. These forces separate the flat disc into rings, agglomerations of material, each ring from which a different planet forms at its central distance from the star (it has a thickness). In a theory of planetary formation from a primordial disc, it should predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of planets today, which was the distribution of the rings from which the planets formed.

Also, the Earth has been in the habitable zone since 4 billion years ago when it was at 0.9 AU. Today it is at 1AU, and that habitable zone can continue to 1.2 AU. So we can speak of the distance to the Earth over much time. The Earth and Sun formed about 4.6 billion years ago. As the Sun very slowly loses mass over millions of years as it burns fuel doing fusion, the Earth slips microscopically further out in its orbit over long periods of time. The Earth orbit increases by about 0.015 meters per year. The Sun only loses 0.00007% of its mass annually. The Earth is at $1\text{AU}=1.496\text{E}11\text{m}$. We have $0.015\text{m}/1.496\text{E}11\text{m}/\text{AU}=1.00267\text{E}-13\text{AU}$. So,

$$(1.00267\text{E} - 13\text{AU}/\text{year})(1\text{E}9\text{years}) = 0.0001\text{AU}$$

The Earth will only move out one ten thousandth of an AU in a billion years. Anatomically modern humans have only been around for about three hundred thousand years. Civilization began only about six thousand years ago.

The unit of a second becomes important in my theory. We got the second from the rotation period of the Earth at the time the moon came to perfectly eclipse the Sun. The Moon slows the Earth rotation and this in turn expands the Moon's orbit, so it is getting larger, the Earth loses energy to the Moon. The Earth day gets longer by 0.0067 hours per million years, and the Moon's orbit gets 3.78 cm larger per year.

That is as the Earth's day gets longer and the lunar orbit grows larger, we got the second at the time that the Earth day was what it is during the epoch when the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun, 24 hours.

The near perfect eclipse is a mystery in the sense that it came to happen when anatomically modern humans arrived on the scene, even before that, perhaps around Homo Erectus and the beginning of the Stone Age. The Earth day was 18 hours long, long before that, 1.4 billion years ago. Homo Erectus is around two to three million years ago.

Introduction I have a theory that could be considered a partial, crude theory of everything. It presents a solution to quantum mechanic's Schrödinger wave equation used for atomic systems, but for planetary systems, in particular for our star system, the Solar System. Also, the theory solves the atom's proton and shows a common characteristic time of about 1 second for both these systems one on the macroscopic scale, star systems, and the other on the microscopic scale, atomic systems, through the atom's proton. Also, in common, it describes hydrocarbons, the chemical skeleton's of life, suggesting that life could be part of a universal process in the Universe. As such, we have a partial theory of everything, but I say partial because it does not, so far, go into particle physics in depth, for instance in treating the quarks that make up protons, or other particles such as photons and electrons.

We want to apply the equations in the theory for our Solar System to other star systems, to see what they don't explain that they do explain in ours, and from that difference find relationships between our star system and others which is where I think we will find not just our purpose but the interconnected purposes between all life in the Universe. I would assume the equations I have found for our star system where the Sun is a yellow, main sequence, spectral class G star would apply for most such stars. But here is an example of how the civilization of one kind of star system could have a relationship with our civilization in terms our star system, the Solar system...

We consider the HR diagram (below) that plots temperature versus luminosity of stars. We see the O, B, A stars are the more luminous stars, which is because they are bigger and more massive and the the F, G stars are medium luminosity, mass, and size (radius). Our Sun is a G star, particularly G2V, the two because the spectral classes are divided up in to 10 sizes, V for five meaning main sequence, that it is part of the S shaped curve and is in the phase where it is burning hydrogen fuel, its original fuel, not the by products. And we see the K and M stars are the coolest, least massive, least luminous.

We consider that the radius of our Sun, R_{\odot} , is about 1.8 times longer than the orbital radius of the Moon, $r_{OurMoon}$. We notice that the mass of a gold atom to the mass of a silver atom is about 1.8 as well which is the same as comparing the molar mass of gold ($Au=196.97$ g/mol) to the molar mass of silver ($Ag=107.87$ g/mol). We have

$$1. \quad R_{\odot} = \frac{Au}{Ag} r_{OurMoon}$$

Gold (Au) and Silver (Ag) have been the primary metals for ceremonial jewelry for Earth civilizations since ancient times. Our Sun is a spectral Class G2V. One spectral class above that is spectral class F. A spectral class F0V star has a radius of about 1.7 solar radii, written $1.7R_{\odot}$. We have the radius of an F0V star

$$2. \quad R_{F0Vstar} = 1.7R_{\odot}$$

As it would turn out, the mass of a silver atom, Ag, to the mass of a copper atom, Cu (comparing their molar masses) is about 1.7. If we are to write

$$3. \quad R_{F0Vstar} = \frac{Ag}{Cu} R_{\odot}$$

$$4. \quad \text{Then, } R_{F0Vstar} = \frac{Ag}{Cu} \frac{Au}{Ag} r_{OurMoon} \text{ and we have}$$

$$5. \quad R_{F0Vstar} = \frac{Au}{Cu} r_{OurMoon}$$

Suggesting perhaps the inhabitants of F0V stars are a copper and silver type civilizations (where ceremonial jewelry is concerned) where we, the inhabitants of our G2V star, are a silver and gold type civilization (where ceremonial jewelry is concerned). This would actually make sense because F0V stars generally have lower metallicities than stars like ours, G2V. Copper and silver being lighter than gold are often more easily formed in environments with lower metallicity. They would be more accessible for a civilization around an F0V star, making them favored for craftsmanship. We also have since $R_{F0Vstar} = 1.7R_{\odot}$ (equation 2)

$$1.7R_{\odot} = 1.7r_{F0Vmoon}$$

$$6. \quad R_{\odot} = r_{F0Vmoon}$$

Which is to say that the orbital radius of the F0V system moon is the radius of our Sun, R_{\odot} .

Something that is further interesting here is that the habitable zone of an F0V star is about as far from the star as the center of the asteroid belt is from our star, the Sun. This is because F0V are more massive and more luminous, as well as larger. Such a star has a mass of 1.61 solar masses (about the golden ratio of the Earth's Sun), a radius of 1.728 solar radii (which is about Ag/Cu), and a luminosity of about 7.24 solar luminosities. By the inverse square law for luminosity such a star has its habitable zone at

$$7. \quad r_{habitable} = \sqrt{7.24L_{\odot}} = 2.7AU$$

The habitable zone our star, the Sun, is where Earth is, 1AU. The asteroid belt in our solar system is at 2.2 to 3.2 AU. Its center is then at 2.7AU. This may represent a shift in concept for a habitable planet around the FoV star. The asteroid belt in our solar system is where a planet can't form. The same distance from an FoV star is where not just a planet can form, but where a habitable planet can form.

Stars like FoV stars would not be as good for hosting life as G2V stars like our Sun because they are bigger and thus hotter meaning they burn up quick leaving less time for intelligence to evolve and become technological. G2V stars like our Sun come just after them, however it is possible that even better than G stars like our Sun are those that come after them in spectral type, the so-called K stars known as orange dwarfs which have even better stability and longer lifespans. Interestingly, we can't apply our theory of ceremonial jewelry to them because these elements, group 11 elements, started before the G star with the F star with copper and silver, which were followed by silver and gold for G stars like our Sun and to go to a K star we have to go to the next element heavier than gold in group 11 and there is only one more which is Roentgenium (Rg). It is extremely radioactive and can only be created in the laboratory. If we move along to the next spectral class, the M stars, they are brown dwarfs and while they can have life and are stable for even longer than K stars (are less massive and cooler) their habitable zones are so close in to the star that when they orbit the star they become tidally locked meaning their orbital period equals their rotation period, which is saying they always have the same side facing the star, and the same side turned away. This means they are very hot on one side and very cold on the other meaning life is optimal only at the edge between one side and the other, in the twilight between always day and always night. This would not be good for doing astronomy and learning about the Universe and your place in it. M brown dwarfs are the most common stars in the Galaxy, if not Universe, and because they are not very bright it is easier to detect planets around them. Most of the planets we have found so far are in such star systems. However, we hope with the advent of the James Webb Space Telescope we will be able to detect Earth-like planets around Sun-like stars like ours. Thus we would conclude that planets with intelligent life are mostly in the F/G/K region of the HR diagrams. We might suggest that copper-silver F star life is less sophisticated than silver-gold G star life like ourselves, but that we are less sophisticated than K star life, which might be the most sophisticated kind. We can look at the stars that come before F stars, the A stars, such as Vega. These stars can have gas giants in their habitable zones with moons that have habitable conditions. We want the radius of the moon in the FoV star system for the habitable planet. We can get this value because we are guessing, as is true in our Solar System that the moon as seen from the habitable planet perfectly eclipses the star as our moon does with our Sun as seen from the Earth. We also know that the orbital radius of the Moon in this system is equation 6, $R_{\odot} = r_{FoVmoon}$.

The condition for a perfect eclipse is

$$8. \quad \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} = \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Which becomes

$$9. \quad \frac{r_{FoVplanet}}{r_{FoVmoon}} = \frac{R_{FoVstar}}{R_{FoVmoon}}$$

Which is

$$10. \quad R_{F0Vmoon} = R_{F0Vstar} \frac{r_{F0Vmoon}}{r_{F0Vplanet}}$$

$$r_{F0Vplanet} = 2.7AU(1.496E11m/AU) = 4E11m$$

$$R_{F0Vstar} = (1.7)(6.96265E8m) = 1.18365E9m$$

$$R_{\odot} = r_{F0Vmoon} = 6.96265E8m$$

$$R_{F0Vmoon} = (1.18365E9m) \frac{(6.96265E8m)}{4E11m} = 2.060E6m$$

Which is exactly the value we wanted to be able to determine because as we will see when I present my theory that the moon of the habitable planet plays a key role in the wave solution to the star system. We see that the Moon of the Earth is a natural yardstick. For instance it gives the radius of our Sun in lunar radii as 400. We see this computation from the radius of the moon of the FoV star is correct because

$$11. \quad \frac{R_{F0Vstar}}{r_{F0Vmoon}} = \frac{1.18365E9}{6.96265E8m} = 1.69999 \approx 1.7 = \frac{Ag}{Cu}$$

We also see

$$12. \quad \frac{R_{\odot}}{r_{OurMoon}} = \frac{6.96265E8m}{3.84E8m} = 1.8132 = \frac{Au}{Ag}$$

We have that $\frac{R_{F0Vmoon}}{R_{OurMoon}} = \frac{2.060}{1.74} = 1.184 \approx 1.2$ (FoV moon 1.2 times bigger than ours).

We have as well

$$13. \quad r_{F0Vmoon} = \frac{Au}{Ag} r_{OurMoon}$$

Making the inhabitants of these F stars our cousins, where we are of the inhabitants of the G stars. We now want to know how the calendar of F star copper-silver civilizations work. To do that we need to know the orbital period of their planet, and the orbital period of their moon. We use Kepler's law

The mass of the star is interestingly about the golden ratio of our Sun's mass, which goes to show another connection between the copper-silver civilizations and silver-gold civilizations. We have

$$(1.61)(1.989E30kg) = 3.2E30kg$$

$$T^2 = \frac{4\pi^2}{GM_{F0Vstar}} r_{F0Vplanet}^3$$

$$\frac{4\pi^2}{GM_{F0Vstar}} = \frac{4\pi^2}{(6.674E-11)(3.2E30kg)} = 1.8485E-19$$

$$T_{F0Vplanet} = \sqrt{(1.8485E-19)(4E11m)^3} = 1.087676E8seconds$$

$$T_{F0Vplanet} = 3.44664years$$

Its planet has year of about 3 and half Earth years. Now we find the orbital period of its moon:

$$T^2 = \frac{4\pi^2}{GM_{F0Vplanet}} r_{F0Vmoon}^3$$

I find if taking the mass of the planet to be a little less than the mass of the Earth — the mass of the earth is 5.972E24kg — we get 16 moons per the planet's year. I think this is what we want. If we use the Earth mass we get 18.82 moons. I find that value is 5E24 kg.

$$T_{F0Vmoon} = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi^2}{(6.674E-11)(5E24kg)} (6.96E8m)^3} = 6315615seconds$$

$$\frac{T_{F0Vplanet}}{T_{F0Vmoon}} = \frac{1E8seconds}{6315615seconds} \approx 16moons$$

I want 16 moons because my guess is that there are two arrays upon which Nature is founded: 12 (3 by 4) and 16 (4 by 4). This occurs not just in physics but in music. The dynamic 12 of flamenco which is a rhythm of two three's plus three two's, and the rumba is four four's, as well as the crux of North Indian classical music which is tin tal played in four, four times, or we also have the 12 bar blues. We have the standard model of particles physics, pictured below, the particles are 6 quarks (lavender) and six leptons (green) make six two times is twelve, and we have the four exchange particles responsible for the forces (in red). Adding these four to the 12 make 16. So the F-star copper-silver civilizations would be 16 moons per year, and the G-star silver gold civilizations would be 12 moons per year, which is what we are.

	fermions (3 générations de la matière)			bosons (forces)
	I	II	III	
masse →	2.4 MeV	1.27 GeV	171.2 GeV	0
charge →	2/3	2/3	2/3	0
spin →	1/2	1/2	1/2	1
nom →	u up	c charm	t top	γ photon
	4.8 MeV	104 MeV	4.2 GeV	0
Quarks	1/3	-1/3	-1/3	0
	1/2	1/2	1/2	1
	d down	s strange	b bottom	g gluon
	<2.2 eV	<0.17 MeV	<15.5 MeV	91.2 GeV
	0	0	0	0
	1/2	1/2	1/2	1
	ν _e neutrino électronique	ν _μ neutrino muonique	ν _τ neutrino tauique	Z ⁰ boson Z ⁰
leptons	0.511 MeV	105.7 MeV	1.777 GeV	80.4 GeV
	-1	-1	-1	±1
	1/2	1/2	1/2	1
	e électron	μ muon	τ tau	W [±] boson W [±]

The twelve moons divided by the 16 moons is 0.75=3/4 and 3 times four is 12. Three to four would be the relationship between copper-silver civilizations and silver-gold civilizations. There may be a reason for it, and it may be rooted in our intertwined destinies that we will learn about when we achieve interstellar space travel and visit these worlds.

1.0 The Theory In my theory, that will be presented in this section and the next, the solution to the Schrödinger wave equation for the atom applied to the Earth/Moon/Sun system, where the Schrödinger wave equation in spherical coordinates is:

1.1

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \right] \psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

and has solutions for the atom as guessed at by Bohr before the wave equation was discovered

$$1.2 \quad E_n = -\frac{Z^2(k_e e^2)^2 m_e}{2\hbar^2 n^2}$$

$$1.3 \quad r_n = \frac{n^2 \hbar^2}{Z k_e e^2 m_e}$$

is

$$1.4 \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$1.5 \quad r_n = \frac{2\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

Where G is the universal constant of gravitation, KE_e is the kinetic energy of the Earth in its orbit around the Sun, M_e is the mass of the Earth, M_m is the mass of the Moon, r_n is the orbital radius of the planet, n the orbital number (is three for Earth), R_\odot is the radius of the Sun, R_m is the radius of the Moon, and \hbar_\odot is a Planck constant associated with the Solar System and is given by

$$1.6 \quad \hbar_\odot = (hC)KE_e$$

$$1.7 \quad hC = 1second$$

Where

$$1.8 \quad C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{G m_p^3}}$$

Where r_p is the radius of a proton, m_p is the mass of a proton, c is the speed of light, and α is the fine structure constant. I found this gives the characteristic time of one second in terms of a proton (Equation 1.7). We guess the planetary scale is connected to the proton scale because the planets formed from the protoplanetary disc are made of different combinations of protons. We derive the value of our solar Planck constant

$$C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi r_p}{Gm_p^3}}$$

$$\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{18769}{299792458} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi(0.833E-15)}{(6.67408E-11)(1.67262E-27)^3}}$$

$$= 1.55976565E33$$

$$= \frac{s}{m} \sqrt{\frac{m}{kg^3} \cdot \frac{s^2 kg}{m^3}} = \frac{s}{m} \sqrt{\frac{s^2}{kg^2 m^2}} = \frac{s}{m} \cdot \frac{s}{kg \cdot m} = \frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2}$$

$$\frac{1}{C} = kg \frac{m^2}{s^2} = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \text{energy}$$

$$hC = (6.62607E-34)(1.55976565E33) = 1.03351 \text{seconds} \approx 1.0 \text{seconds}$$

$$hC = \left(kg \frac{m}{s^2} \cdot m \cdot s \right) \left(\frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2} \right)$$

$$= \left(kg \frac{m^2}{s} \right) \left(\frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2} \right) = \text{seconds}$$

$$KE_{\text{earth}} = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24 kg) (30,290 m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33 J$$

$$1.9 \quad \hbar_{\odot} = (hC) KE_{\text{earth}} = (1.03351s)(2.7396E33J) = 2.8314E33J \cdot s$$

Where we used the maximum orbital velocity of the Earth (perihelion). We notice the kinetic energy of the Earth is given by not just the mass of the Earth, but by the mass of the Moon looking at equation 1.4:

$$KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

n is the orbital number of the Earth, which is 3. You will notice the radius of the sun, R_{\odot} , and the radius of the Moon, R_m , factors into the solution, which is because we are dealing with not just an atom, but a planetary orbital system, which forms not just from the inverse square law of the Newton's gravity due to the Sun like occurs in the atom with electric fields, but has the rotational centripetal force of the protoplanetary cloud from which the planets formed, and the outward radiation pressure from the Sun. We guessed that the mass of the the Moon figured in instead of the Sun, and that the characteristic time for determining the Planck-type constant for the solar system in terms of the kinetic energy of the Earth was 1 second because I had found that it is approximately true that:

$$1.10 \quad 1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

Where KE_m is the kinetic energy of the Moon and EarthDay is the the rotation period of the Earth (about 24 hours). It in fact may be that the fact that the Moon as seen from the Earth nearly perfectly eclipses the Sun is a condition for optimal habitability of the Earth. That is for habitable planets:

$$1.11 \quad \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

That is the orbital radius of the planet (Earth) to the orbital radius of its moon (The Moon) is about equal to the the radius of the star (The Sun) to the radius of its moon (The Moon). We say the system is quantized by the Moon and the base unit of one second. It is a fact that the Moon orbiting the Earth optimizes the conditions for life on Earth because it holds the Earth at its inclination to its orbit around the Sun allowing for the seasons, preventing extreme hot and extreme cold.

We find our unit of one second pans out nearly perfect in deriving the ground state for the Solar System by writing

$$1.12 \quad M_m^3 = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{1second} \cdot \frac{1}{Gc}$$

Where c is the speed of light. We consider equation 1.4

$$1.4 \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

We want to eliminate \hbar_{\odot} from the equation because we don't know if it is the same for star systems other than ours, the Solar System. 1.12 and 1.4 yield

$$1.13 \quad KE_e = \sqrt{3} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{GM_p^2}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{(1sec)c}$$

Using the fact the the orbital velocity of the Earth is

$$v_e = \sqrt{\frac{GM_{\odot}}{r_e}}$$

And,

$$KE_e = \frac{1}{2} M_e v_e^2$$

We have

$$1.14 \quad \sqrt{3}M_e \cdot \frac{r_e}{R_m} \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{M_\odot} = (1second)c$$

We use equation 1.11

$$\frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

It is

$$1.15 \quad \frac{r_e}{r_m} \approx \frac{R_\odot}{R_m}$$

Which can be written

$$1.16 \quad R_m = R_\odot \frac{r_m}{r_e}$$

So equation 1.14 becomes

$$1.17 \quad \sqrt{3} \frac{M_e}{M_\odot} \cdot \frac{r_e^2}{r_m} = (1second)c$$

Which can be written

$$1.18 \quad r_m = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{(1sec)c} \cdot \frac{M_e}{M_\odot} \cdot r_e^2$$

We now want to write this in a general form not just Earth mass but planet mass, and not just solar mass but stellar mass. We have

$$1.19 \quad r_m = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{(1sec)c} \cdot \frac{M_p}{M_\star} \cdot r_p^2$$

2.0 The Proton I said my theory predicts the Earth/Moon/Sun system and the atom's proton to have a characteristic time of a second in common. Let's show this more explicitly than I presented so far. I found 1 second is the base unit of the orbital dynamics of the solar system. I find I can create three spacetime operators, one that acts on the radius of the proton to its mass, and the other that acts on the radius of the Sun to its mass, and one that acts on angular momentum to speed. h is Planck's constant, G is the universal constant of gravitation, c is the speed of light, α is the fine structure constant, r_p is the radius of a proton, m_p is the mass of a proton, M_m is the mass of the Moon, R_m is its radius, and the EarthDay is the rotation period of the Earth:

$$2.1 \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$2.2 \quad \left(\frac{M_m(EarthDay)}{R_m} \right) \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{M_\odot} = 1second$$

$$2.3 \quad \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

They seem to suggest that the Earth orbit might be quantized in terms of the Moon and a base unit of one second, which we will see can be considered a characteristic time of the Universe. Equation 2.2 is actually 1.3 seconds but rounds to one second. However it is derived from another equation that gives 1.2 seconds. Namely, equation 1.10:

$$1second = \frac{KE_m(EarthDay)}{KE_e}$$

It says one second is the Earth Day (completion of one rotation of the Earth) adjusted by the kinetic energy of the Moon, to the kinetic energy of the Earth.

We see the spacetime operators solve the atom by giving us the radius of a proton. We set equation 2.1 equal to equation 2.3

$$2.3 \quad \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

$$2.1 \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

These two yield

$$2.4 \quad r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c m_p}$$

I find this is close to the experimental value of the radius of a proton. I find I can arrive at this radius of a proton another way, energy is given by Planck's constant and frequency

$$E = hf$$

We have

$$f = 1/s, h = J \cdot s, hf = (J \cdot s)(1/s) = J$$

$E = J = \text{Joules} = \text{energy}$

We take the rest energy of the mass of a proton m_p :

$$E = m_p c^2$$

The frequency of a proton is

$$f_p = \frac{m_p c^2}{h}$$

Since our theory gave us the factor of $2/3$ for the radius of a proton we have:

$$\frac{m_p c^2}{h} \cdot \frac{r_p}{c} = \frac{2}{3} \approx \phi = \frac{m_p c}{h} r_p$$

$$m_p r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c}$$

The radius of a proton is then

$$r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c m_p}$$

This is very close to the value upon which the proton radius converged historically by two independent methods which was $0.877\text{E}-15\text{m}$. The result from our theory is

$$r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{6.62607\text{E} - 34}{(299,792,458)(1.67262\text{E} - 27)} = 0.88094\text{E} - 15\text{m}$$

The 0.877fm was challenged in 2010 by a third experiment making it 4% smaller and was $0.842\text{E}-15\text{m}$. We find it may be that the radius of a proton is actually

$$2.5 \quad r_p = \phi \cdot \frac{h}{c m_p} = 0.816632\text{E} - 15\text{m}$$

Where ϕ is the golden ratio constant (0.618...). This is more along the lines of more recent measurements. Both equations 2.4 and 2.5 for the radius of the proton can be right depending on the dynamics of what is going on; the radius of a proton is not precisely defined, it is more of a fuzzy cloud of subatomic particles. Thus we have solved the atom with our spacetime operators by producing the radius of a proton. I began working on this theory when the proton radius was 0.833 fm so it is what I have been using in this paper. We continue to be honing in on its experimental value every year with more experiments. The vast gap between the historical 0.877fm and the 2010 0.842fm is known in physics as the proton puzzle.

Indeed over the full range of values for the radius of a proton, the characteristic time is very close to one second. The large value they got a long time ago gives:

$$\left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1 \text{second}$$

$$\frac{(18769)((0.88094E - 15m))}{6(1.67262E - 27kg)} \sqrt{\frac{(6.62607E - 34J \cdot s)(4\pi)}{(6.674E - 11)(299,792,458m/s)}} = 1.06284 \text{seconds}$$

The current value, which they believe they have really closed in on as very accurate in two different experiments in 2019 using different methods, which is $r_p = 0.833E - 15m$, gives a time of 1.00500 seconds.

Let us consider the radius of a proton is

$$r_p = \phi \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p} = 0.816632E - 15m$$

If we can say that the radius of a proton is always the same value, which we can't because it depends on what is going on, we might say it is usually this like the classical radius of an electron is used in most problems. However, here we are using it as it applies to the formation of the planets from the protoplanetary disc made-up of these protons. If and when the proton radius is this, then the spacetime operators are

$$2.1 \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1 \text{second}$$

$$2.2 \quad \left(\frac{M_m(\text{EarthDay})}{R_m} \right) \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{M_\odot} = 1 \text{second}$$

$$2.3 \quad \left(\sqrt{\phi \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1 \text{second}$$

In which case

$$\left(\sqrt{\phi \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1 \text{second}$$

$$= \sqrt{(0.618) \frac{(352,275,361)\pi(0.833E - 15m)}{(6.674E - 11)(1.67262E - 27)^3} \frac{1}{3} \frac{(6.62607E - 34)}{(299792458)}}$$

$$= 0.9950796 \text{ seconds} \sim 1 \text{second}$$

The condition for a perfect eclipse:

$$\frac{R_{\odot}}{R_{moon}} = \frac{r_{earth}}{r_{moon}}$$

Which says the radius of the Sun to the radius of the Moon equals the Earth orbital radius to the lunar orbital radius are equal does indicate that the Earth/Moon/Sun system converges on the basis unit of one second of time for the solution of the Schrödinger wave equation during the time we are in where such an eclipse happens. That is the basis unit of time in the solution is given by

$$2.6. \quad \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1second$$

It may be this eclipse condition is the condition for the optimization of the habitability of the Earth. We can show that the epoch that this condition holds gives the unit of a second as the solution by using it to form a solar solution to the wave equation and equating it with our lunar solution. Let's do that now...

3.0 The Solar Formulation Our solution of the wave equation for the planets gives the kinetic energy of the Earth from the mass of the Moon orbiting the Earth, but you could formulate based on the Earth orbiting the Sun. In our lunar formulation we had:

$$3.1 \quad KE_e = \sqrt{3} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

We remember the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun which is to say

$$3.2 \quad \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} = \frac{r_e}{r_m}$$

Thus equation 3.1 becomes

$$3.3 \quad KE_e = \sqrt{3} \frac{r_e}{r_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$3.4 \quad KE_e = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{GM_{\odot} M_e}{r_e}$$

Putting this in equation 3.3 gives the mass of the Sun:

$$3.5 \quad M_{\odot} = \sqrt{3} r_e^2 \cdot \frac{GM_e}{r_m} \cdot \frac{M_m^3}{\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

We recognize that the orbital velocity of the Moon is

$$3.6 \quad v_m^2 = \frac{GM_e}{r_m}$$

So equation 3.5 becomes

$$3.7 \quad M_\odot = \sqrt{3}r_e^2 \cdot v_m^2 \cdot \frac{M_m^3}{\hbar_\odot^2}$$

This gives the mass of the Moon is

$$3.8 \quad M_m^3 = \frac{M_\odot \hbar_\odot^2}{\sqrt{3}r_e^2 v_m^2}$$

Putting this in equation 3.1 yields

$$3.9 \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_\odot}{2r_e^2 v_m^2}$$

We now multiply through by M_e^2/M_e^2 and we have

$$3.10 \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2r_e^2 v_m^2 M_e^2}$$

Thus the Planck constant for the Sun, \hbar_\odot , in this case the star is the Sun, is angular momentum quantized, the angular momentum we will call L_p , the subscript p for Planck. We have

$$L_p = r_e v_m M_e = r_e v_m M_e = (1.496E11m)(1022m/s)(5.972E24kg) = 9.13E38kg \cdot \frac{m^2}{s}$$

$$L_p^2 = r_e^2 v_m^2 M_e^2 = 7.4483E77J \cdot m^2 \cdot kg = 8.3367E77kg^2 \cdot \frac{m^4}{s^2}$$

We write for the solution of the Earth/Sun system:

$$3.11 \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2L_p^2}$$

We can write 3.11 as

$$3.12 \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

We say. $\hbar_\odot = \hbar_\odot/2\pi$. That is

$$\hbar_\odot = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

$$h_{\odot} = 2\pi\hbar_{\odot} = 5.7365E39J \cdot s$$

Let us see how accurate our equation is:

$$\begin{aligned} KE_e &= \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_{\odot}}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2} \\ &= \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2 (5.972E24kg)^4 (1.9891E30kg)}{2(8.3367E77kg^2 \cdot \frac{m^4}{s^2})} \\ &= \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} (6.759E30J) \\ \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} &= \frac{6.957E8m}{1737400m} = 400.426 \end{aligned}$$

$$KE_e = 2.70655E33J$$

We have that the kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_{earth} = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24kg) (30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J$$

Our equation has an accuracy of

$$\frac{2.70655E33J}{2.7396E33J} = 98.79\%$$

Which is very good.

We call L_p the same \hbar_{\odot} in our solar solution. But we now want our r_n solution for the solar formulation. M_e is the mass of the Earth and M_{\odot} is the mass of the Sun. We have our solution might be

$$3.13 \quad r_n = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_e^3} \cdot \frac{R_m}{R_{\odot}}$$

Where \hbar_{\odot} is

$$\hbar_{\odot} = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

We have

$$3.14 \quad r_3 = \frac{(9.13E38)^2}{(6.67408E-11)(5.972E24kg)^3} \cdot \frac{1}{400.5986} = 1.4638E11m$$

This has an accuracy of

$$\frac{1.4638E11m}{1.496E11m}100 = 97.85 \%$$

Thus the solutions to the wave equation

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \right] \psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

for the solar formulations are

$$3.15 \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$3.16 \quad r_n = \frac{\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_e^3} \cdot \frac{R_m}{R_\odot}$$

$$\hbar_\odot = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

$$h_\odot = 2\pi\hbar_\odot = 5.7365E39J \cdot s$$

4.0 Equating The Lunar And Solar Formulations Yield Our 1 Second Base Unit

Let us equate equation 1.4 with equation 3.12:

$$1.1 \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$3.12 \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$\sqrt{3} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2} = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2L_p^2}$$

This gives:

$$4.1 \quad L_p = \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} \cdot \hbar_\odot$$

We remember that

$$\hbar_\odot = (hC)KE_p$$

$$hC = 1second$$

$$C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi r_p}{Gm_p^3}}$$

$$\frac{1}{6\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1.004996352seconds$$

This gives

$$4.2 \quad r_e v_m M_e = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi}{Gc}} \cdot \frac{1}{2} M_e v_e^2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}}$$

We have

$$4.3 \quad 2v_m = \frac{v_e^2}{r_e} (1second) \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}}$$

This equates the orbital velocity of the Moon with the centripetal acceleration of the Earth in terms of one second by way of the mass of the Earth, the mass of the Sun, the mass of the Moon, and the orbital number of the Earth. Let us compute

$$4.4 \quad \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} = \sqrt{\frac{(5.972E24kg)^2 (1.9891E30kg)}{(7.34763E22kg)^3 (1.732)}} = 321,331.459 \approx 321,331$$

Let us see how well equation 19 works. v_m at aphelion is 966 m/s and $v_e = 29,800m/s$. $r_e = 1AU = 1.496E11m$. We have

$$2(966m/s) = \frac{(29,800m/s)^2}{1.496E11m} (1sec)(321,331.459)$$

$$1,907m/s = 1,932m/s$$

That is an accuracy of

$$\frac{1907}{1932} = 98.7\%$$

Equation 4.3 can be written:

$$4.5 \quad 1second = 2r_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

In terms of other star systems this is

$$4.5 \quad 1 \text{ second} = 2r_p \frac{v_m}{v_p^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_p^2 M_\star}}$$

5.0 The Solutions For Jupiter and Saturn

Now we want to find what the wave equation solutions are for Jupiter and Saturn because they significantly carry the majority of the mass of the solar system and thus should embody most clearly the dynamics of the wave solution to the Solar System.

I find that as we cross the asteroid belt leaving behind the terrestrial planets, which are solid, and go to the gas giants and ice giants, the atomic number is no longer squared and the square root of the the orbital number moves from the numerator to the denominator. I believe this is because the solar system here should be modeled in two parts, just as it is in theories of solar system formation because there is a force other than just gravity of the Sun at work, which is the radiation pressure of the Sun, which is what separates it into two parts, the terrestrial planets on this side of the asteroid belt and the giants on the other side of the asteroid belt. The effect the radiation pressure has is to blow the lighter elements out beyond the asteroid belt when the solar system forms, which are gases such as hydrogen and helium, while the heavier elements are too heavy to be blown out from the inside of the asteroid belt, allowing for the formation of the terrestrial planets Venus, Earth, and Mars. The result is that our equation has the atomic number of the heavier metals such as calcium for the Earth, while the equation for the giants has the atomic numbers of the gasses. We write for these planets

$$E = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{n}} \frac{G^2 M^2 m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

So, for Jupiter we have (And again using the maximum orbital velocity which is at perihelion):

$$KE_j = \frac{1}{2}(1.89813E27kg)(13720m/s)^2 = 1.7865E35J$$

$$E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}} \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2(1.89813E27kg)^2(7.347673E22kg)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2}$$

$$E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}}(3.971E35J) = Z_H(1.776E35J)$$

$$Z_H = \frac{1.7865E35J}{1.776E35J} = 1.006 \text{ protons} \approx 1.0 \text{ protons} = \text{hydrogen}(H)$$

Jupiter is mostly composed of hydrogen gas, and secondly helium gas, so it is appropriate that $Z = Z_H$.

Our equation for Jupiter is

$$5.1 \quad E_5 = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}} \frac{G^2 M_j^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

Where Z_H is the atomic number of hydrogen which is 1 proton, and $\sqrt{n} = \sqrt{5}$ for the orbital number of Jupiter, $n = 5$. Now we move on to Saturn...

$$KE_s = \frac{1}{2} (5.683E26kg)(10140m/s)^2 = 2.92E34J$$

$$E = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{6}} \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2 (5.683E26kg)^2 (7.347673E22)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2}$$

$$= \frac{Z}{2.45} (3.5588E34J) = Z(1.45259E34J)$$

$$Z(1.45259E34J) = (2.92E34J)$$

$$Z = 2 \text{ protons} = \text{Helium (He)}$$

The equation for Saturn is then

$$5.2 \quad E_6 = \frac{Z_{He}}{\sqrt{6}} \frac{G^2 M_s^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

It makes sense that Saturn would use Helium in the equation because Saturn is the next planet after Jupiter and Jupiter uses hydrogen, and helium is the next element after hydrogen. As well, just like Jupiter, Saturn is primarily composed of hydrogen and helium gas.

The accuracy for Earth orbit is

$$E_n = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

$$\frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} = \frac{6.96E8m}{1737400m} = 400.5986$$

$$E_3 = (1.732)(400.5986) \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2 (5.972E24kg)^2 (7.347673E22kg)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2} =$$

$$= 2.727E36J$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_e = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24kg)(30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J$$

$$\frac{2.727E36J}{2.7396E33J} 100 = 99.5 \%$$

Which is very good, about 100% for all practical purposes. The elemental expression of the solution for the Earth would be

$$5.3. \quad E_3 = \sqrt{3} \frac{Z_{Ca}^2 G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

Where

$$\frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \rightarrow Z^2$$

In this case the element associated with the Earth is calcium which is Z=20 protons.

6.0 The Origin of a Second It is worth looking at ancient systems of looking at time because that is where the origins of our current systems began. Indeed our system came from the ancient Sumerians and Babylonians. They divided the day into 12 units where the day is given by the rising and setting of the Sun, which in turn is given by the period of the rotation of the Earth. Thus the day was given by the period from the rising of the Sun to its setting, which was divided into 12 units which we call, today, hours. Thus the day from sunrise to sunrise, or sunset to sunset, is 24 hours. Why they chose 12 units could come from the fact that 12 is the smallest abundant number, which means it has a lot of divisors: 1, 2, 3, 4, 6. Abundant means their sum is greater than 12 itself: $1+2+3+4+6=16$. We know for certain they chose 12 because there are three sections on each finger, so with 4 such fingers you can touch each such section with your thumb to count to twelve. The Babylonians got base 60 from the Sumerians and further divided each hour into 60 minutes, and each minute into 60 seconds. Why base 60 was chosen is that it has a lot of divisors as well, including the first 6 integers. It is the smallest number that does this.

We see dividing the day into 24 hours and dividing that further with base 60 leads to the duration of a second we have today. Only on planet Earth would we have the primitive, ancient origins of our mathematics in the end line up with modern physics in that, as it would turn out, it gave us our basis unit of a second to be a natural constant. Though we could guess that on other planets the ancient civilizations when first inventing mathematics and astronomy, would use base 60 because it is so convenient for doing math being evenly divisible by the first 6 integers. However, we did that and combined it with divisions of 24 units. Not necessarily would any planet do that. However, we had other reasons to do that; the Moon orbits the Earth close to 12 times in the time it takes the Earth to go once around the Sun. However, there is an ancient system where the people didn't divide the day into 24 units, but rather into 60 units, meaning that their hour was 24 minutes long. That is $(24\text{hours})(60\text{min}/\text{hour}) = 1440\text{min}/\text{day}$ and $1440\text{minutes}/60 = 24\text{minutes}/\text{hour}$. This was the Vedic time-keeping system in ancient India. Leave it to the Hindu Indians to have extraterrestrial intelligence in their ancient beginnings. So let's go into this. We will see that base 60 combined with 24 describes the angular momentum of the Earth. That means it doesn't just include the rotation period of the Earth, but the size of the Earth (its radius) and the mass of the Earth.

Indeed if the dynamics of the factors the ancients gave us to create the duration of a second are connected to the dynamics of star systems then the second should define the rotational angular momentum of the Earth since we divide the rotation period of the Earth into these factors to get the unit of second, and should be connected to our Planck constant for the solar system which is in units of angular momentum as well, as is Planck's constant for the atom.

The angular momentum of the Earth with respect to the Sun is $2.66E40 \text{ kg m}^2/\text{s}$. The rotational angular momentum is $7.05E33 \text{ kg m}^2/\text{s}$. In orbit angular momentum is given by

$$L = 2\pi Mfr^2$$

For a uniform rotational sphere it is given by

$$L = \frac{4}{5}\pi Mfr^2$$

We found our solar system Planck constant was

$$\hbar_{\odot} = 2.8314E33J \cdot s$$

This gives

$$6.1. \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} = \frac{7.05E33}{2.8314E33} = 2.4899 \approx 2.5 = 2\frac{1}{2}$$

We are now equipped to show that the ancient Sumerians were right in dividing the rotation period of the Earth (the day) into 24 units (the hour) because

$$2.5(24) = 60$$

That is

$$6.2. \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

Which is to say the angular momentum of the Earth to its Planck constant gives the base 60 counting in terms of the 24 hour day, the 60 of 60 minutes in an hour, and 60 seconds in a minute, that determine our base unit of duration we call a second that happens to be, as I have shown, the base unit of the wave solution to the atom and the Earth/Moon/Sun system.

Our equation in this paper for the Earth energy as a solution of the wave equation 1.4

$$1.4 \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

does not depend on the Moon's distance from the Earth, only its mass. The Moon slows the Earth rotation and this in turn expands the Moon's orbit, so it is getting larger, the Earth loses energy to the Moon. The Earth day gets longer by 0.0067 hours per million years, and the Moon's orbit gets 3.78 cm larger per year. Equation 6.2

$$6.2. \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

only specifies divide the day into 24 units, and hours into 60 minutes and minutes into 60 seconds, regardless of what the Earth rotational velocity is. But it was more or less the same as it is now when the Sumerians started civilization. But it may be that it holds for when the Earth day is such that when the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun, which we said might be a condition for the optimization of life preventing extreme hot and cold. That is when the following holds

$$\frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Which holds for today and held for the ancient Sumerians and holds for when the Earth rotation gives the duration of a second we have today.

We want the basis set of equations for the solar system. We have

$$\lambda_{moon} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} = 3.0281E8m$$

We have from equation

$$\frac{\lambda_{moon}}{c} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1.0seconds$$

and,

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (hC)KE_e$$

$$hC = 1second$$

From these it becomes clear that

$$6.3. \quad \hbar_{\odot} = \frac{GM_m^3 c}{KE_e}$$

$$6.4. \quad KE_e = \frac{GM_m^3 c}{\hbar_{\odot}}$$

Thus combining equation 6.2 with the following...

$$6.2. \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

We write

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (1second)KE_e$$

From 6.3 we have

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (1second) \frac{GM_m^3 c}{\hbar_{\odot}}$$

$$\hbar_{\odot}^2 = (1second)GM_m^3 c$$

Which gives us

$$\begin{aligned} 6.5. \quad 1second &= \left(\frac{24}{60}\right)^2 \frac{L_{earth}^2}{GM_m^3 c} \\ &= \left(\frac{24}{60}\right)^2 \frac{(7.05E33)^2}{(6.67408E-11)((7.347673E22kg)^3(299792458m/s)} = \\ &\left(\frac{24}{60}\right)^2 6.262sec = 1.002seconds = 1.00seconds \end{aligned}$$

This is very accurate to give us a second. But notice 6.262 is approximately 2π . We see that

$$6.6. \quad 1 = \left(\frac{24}{60}\right)^2 2\pi$$

2π is the circumference of a unit circle, it could be that the circumference of the Earth orbit, can be taken as 1 (unity) and essentially we have the mystery of base 60 and the 24 hour day of the ancient Sumerians is solved, it connects the circumference of a unit circle to 1 (unity).

$$6.7. \quad \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} = \frac{24}{60}\sqrt{\pi}$$

$$6.8. \quad \cos(45^\circ) = \cos(\pi/4) = \frac{24}{60}\sqrt{\pi}$$

The Hindu Vedic System has a day is 60 ghatika of 24 minutes each, each ghatika is divided into 60 palas of 24 seconds each, and each pala is divided into 60 vispalas, each vispala of 0.4 seconds each. So where our system has a base unit of 1 second, theirs has a base unit of 0.4 seconds, so that could be an advantage to their system, a smaller unit of time is more refined. Further their day is divided into 60 units, ours into only 24, so their hour, the ghatika is only 24 minutes long, and ours is 60 minutes long, The proponents of this system in India say since when working and doing chores we do a few chores in an hour, they do about one per ghatika is 24 minutes, which makes the measure of time more manageable. That could be an advantage I think. They say our hour is so long because the lines had to be far apart on the Egyptian Sun Dial so the shadow cast by the Sun didn't cross-over onto another line. But today, with modern technology we can make clock lines marking hours closer together and measure them with a pointer hand pointing to them without any problems, and the result is we would have a smaller more refined hour (60 of them in a day as opposed to 24). They suggest this method of measuring time would work better in science and engineering as well, that we have to get away from the way sun dials had to be made in Egypt in ancient times.

But they further point out that their system describes Nature. They say theirs are 108,000 vispalas in a day, and 108,000 vispalas in a night giving 216,000 vispalas in a 24 hour day. The diameter of the Sun is 108 that of the Earth, and the average distance from the Sun to the Earth is 108 solar diameters, and the average distance from the Moon to Earth is 108 lunar diameters. $108(10)(10)(10)=108,000$. Ourselves and them use base 10 counting, and that is probably because we have ten fingers to count on.

The incredible thing here is that the wonderful equations:

$$\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} = \frac{7.05E33}{2.8314E33} = 2.4899 \approx 2.5 = 2\frac{1}{2}$$

$$\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

unify the Mesopotamian system with the Hindu system because

$$1vispala = 0.4seconds$$

$$(0.4s)(2.5) = 1second$$

This suggests that the Hindu system is just as Natural as the Western system.

We have said the ancient Sumerians gave us the duration of a second we have today by dividing up the rotation period of the Earth into 24 units we call hours, which the Babylonians divided into 60 minutes and 60 seconds that they got from the Sumerian base 60. We have found in my theory that the 1 second is a natural constant because it is the base unit of our solution to both the solar system and the atom. We further found the Hindu's used similar numbers in an inverted way to the way of the West that came from the Sumerians, and that their system relates not just to the West's but to our theory in a dynamic way concerning the angular momentum of the Earth and our Planck constant for the Solar system.

The Sumerians of Mesopotamia and the Hindus of the Indus Valley Civilization were of the first civilizations, but so was Egypt. If the second was in Mesopotamia and in India, it was only necessary to find it in Egypt. Since the Earth spin has been the natural clock for which the humans first measured time since ancient times, the rising and setting of the Sun due to it, I looked at how much distance through which the earth rotates at its equator in one second. It is, since this distance is

$$s = r\theta$$

where theta is in radians, and the the radius of the Earth is 6.378E6m. The earth rotates through 360 degrees per 24 hours, or per 86,400 seconds = 0.004167 degrees per second = 7.27E-5 radians. We have

$$s = (6.378E6m)(7.27E - 5rad) = 464m = 0.464km = 0.2883mi \approx 0.3mi$$

If the second was to exist in ancient times in Egypt we should see it in the Great Pyramids. The three largest are in a line and are separated by

Khufu to Khafre (0.25 miles)

Khafre to Menkaure (0.3 miles)

We see the second and third pyramids built, Khafre and Menkaure, which were built in the 25th century BC and were of the the 4th dynasty of the old kingdom, are 0.3 miles apart, the distance through which the Earth rotates in one second, the one second we found to be a natural constant at the basis of the the atom and solar system.

The ancient Sumerians say they got there mathematics in their writings from the Gods who came to Earth from the sky they called the Anunaki. Some have suggested the Anunaki were ancient aliens. The Ancient Egyptians built enormous pyramids from heavy stones weighing tons, somehow lifted 50 feet to be stacked in near perfect mathematical proportions. This has been a deep mystery in Archaeology. Again some suggest ancient aliens here. I have shown all three of these civilizations have a system of measurement (the Egyptians had a 24 hour day as well) that is intrinsic to the laws of nature describing the atom and the solar system in modern times. It can be suggested that the second was given to them by ancient aliens.

A really good find is the following...

My theory suggests the Sumerians could have ultimately got the unit of a second for measuring time from ancient Aliens, they called the Anunaki who they say came from the sky. The same second I have found is characteristic of our solar system and the proton. Scholars have puzzled over the the depiction in Sumerian art of the strange watch-like bracelets around the wrists of the Anunaki gods, who they say came from the sky and gave them mathematics. They have twelve divisions like our clocks today have because the 12 and 6 o'clock positions have two pointers running together as one.

7.0 Integrating Analytic and Wave Solutions of the Solar System We would like to see how our wave solution for the solar system figures into the classical analytic theory of the formation of our solar system. The protoplanetary disc that evolves into the planets has two forces that balance its pressure, the centripetal force of the gas disc due to its rotation around the protostar v_ϕ^2/r and the inward gravitational force on the disc from the protostar GM_\star/r^2 , and these are related by ρ the density of the gas that makes up the disc. The pressure gradient of the disc in radial equilibrium balancing the inward gravity and outward centripetal force is

$$7.1. \quad \frac{dP}{dr} = -\rho \left(\frac{GM_\star}{r^2} - \frac{v_\phi^2}{r} \right)$$

We can solve this for pressure in the protoplanetary disc as a function of r , distance from the star, as follows: Assume the gas is isothermal, meaning the temperature T is constant so we can relate pressure and density with

$$P = c_s^2 \rho$$

Where c_s is the speed of sound in the gas which depends on its temperature. We take the gas to be in nearly Keplerian rotation. That is the rotation is given by Newtonian gravity:

$$v_K = \sqrt{\frac{GM_\star}{r}}$$

And we take into account that the rotational velocity is slowed down by gas pressure using the parameter η which is less than one:

$$v_\phi = v_K(1 - \eta)$$

We can say for a protoplanetary disc like that from which our solar system originated that its density varies with radius as a power law:

$$\rho(r) = \rho_0 \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{-s}$$

ρ_0 is the reference density at r_0 and s is the power law exponent. We can write

$$v_\phi^2 = v_K^2(1 - \eta)^2 \approx \frac{GM_\star}{r}(1 - 2\eta).$$

We have from 7.1:

$$7.2. \quad \frac{dP}{dr} = -\rho \left(\frac{GM_\star}{r^2 \cdot 2\eta} \right)$$

Since $P = c_s^2 \rho$, we have that $dP/dr = c_s^2 d\rho/dr$ which gives from 2:

$$\frac{d\rho}{\rho} = -\frac{2\eta GM_{\star}}{c_s^2 r^2} dr$$

We integrate both sides:

$$\int_{\rho_0}^{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{\rho} = -\frac{2\eta GM_{\star}}{c_s^2 r^2} \int_{r_0}^r r_0 dr$$

And, we have

$$\ln\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right) = \frac{2\eta GM_{\star}}{c_s^2} \left(\frac{1}{r_0} - \frac{1}{r}\right)$$

$$\rho(r) = \rho_0 \exp\left[\frac{2\eta GM_{\star}}{c_s^2} \left(\frac{1}{r_0} - \frac{1}{r}\right)\right]$$

$$7.3 \quad P_0 = c_s^2 \rho_0 \exp\left[\frac{2\eta GM_{\star}}{c_s^2} \left(\frac{1}{r_0} - \frac{1}{r}\right)\right]$$

We take

$$\frac{2\eta GM_{\star}}{c_s^2} \left(\frac{1}{r_0} - \frac{1}{r}\right)$$

as small because η is small and r is large so we can make the approximation $e^x \approx 1 + x$. We have

$$7.4. \quad P_r \approx P_0 \left[1 + \frac{2\eta GM_{\star}}{c_s^2} \left(\frac{1}{r_0} - \frac{1}{r}\right)\right]$$

$$P_0 = c_s^2 \rho_0$$

What we can get out of this is since the deviation parameter, η , is given by

$$7.5. \quad \eta = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{c_s}{v_K}\right)^2 \frac{d \ln P}{d \ln R} \text{ and}$$

$$7.6. \quad c_s = \sqrt{\frac{k_B T}{\mu m_H}}$$

Where, $k_B = 1.38E - 23J/K$ is the Boltzmann constant, $\mu \approx 2.3$ is the molecular weight of hydrogen, and m_H is the mass of hydrogen is basically the mass of a proton is $1.67E-27\text{kg}$. Since for a protoplanetary cloud at Earth orbit T is around 280 degrees Kelvin we have

$$c_s = 1km/s$$

Typically in discs the pressure decreases with radius as a power law

$$P(R) \propto R^{-q}$$

Where $q \approx 2.5$, so

$$7.7. \quad \frac{d \ln P}{d \ln R} \approx -2.5$$

$$\eta = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1km/s}{30km/s} \right)^2 (-2.5) = 1.5E-3$$

So, essentially, by the chain rule

$$\frac{d \ln P}{d \ln R} = \frac{d \ln P}{d R} \cdot \frac{d R}{d \ln R} = \frac{1}{P} \frac{d P}{d R} \cdot R = \frac{R}{P} \frac{d P}{d R}$$

to clarify things. The reason 7.7 is significant is that equation

$$\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} = \frac{7.05E33}{2.8314E33} = 2.4899 \approx 2.5 = 2\frac{1}{2}$$

Where

$$L_{earth} = \frac{4}{5} \pi M_e f_e R_e^2$$

$$\hbar_{\odot} = 2.8314E33J \cdot s$$

$$\frac{\lambda_{moon}}{c} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1.0seconds$$

The spacetime operators are...

$$1) \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$2) \quad \left(\frac{M_m(EarthDay)}{R_m} \right) \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{M_\odot} = 1second$$

$$3) \quad \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

So we have

$$7.8. \quad \frac{R}{P} \frac{dP}{dR} = - \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_\odot}$$

We have

$$7.9. \quad \frac{dP}{P} = - \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_\odot} \frac{dR}{R}$$

Integrate both sides

$$\int \frac{dP}{P} = - \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_\odot} \int \frac{dR}{R}$$

$$\ln P = - \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_\odot} \ln R + C$$

If P_0 is the reference pressure at the reference radius R_0 then the pressure as a function of radius for the protoplanetary disc from which our solar system formed is:

$$7.10. \quad P(R) = P_0 \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right)^{-\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_\odot}} \quad \text{or,} \quad P(R) = P_0 \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right) \exp \left[-\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_\odot} \right]$$

Where

$$L_{earth} = \frac{4}{5} \pi M_e f_e R_e^2$$

$$\hbar_\odot = \sqrt{GM_m^3 c (1second)} \quad \text{from} \quad \frac{\lambda_{moon}}{c} = \frac{\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1.0seconds$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1 \text{second}$$

8.0 A Theory For Biological Hydrocarbons I have found that the basis unit of one second is not just a Natural constant for physical systems like the atom and the planets around the Sun but for the basis of biological life, that it is in the sixfold Nature of the chemical skeletons from which life is built, the hydrocarbons. I found

$$1). \quad 1second = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}}$$

$$2). \quad 1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

Where $\alpha = 1/137$ is the fine structure constant, r_p is the radius of a proton, m_p is the mass of a proton, h is Planck's constant, G is the constant of gravitation, c is the speed of light, KE_m is the kinetic energy of the Moon, KE_e is the kinetic energy of the Earth, and *EarthDay* is the rotation period of the Earth is one day.

The first can be written:

$$3). \quad \frac{1}{\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h 4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 6proton \cdot seconds = carbon(C)$$

$$4). \quad \frac{1}{\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h 4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1proton \cdot 6seconds = hydrogen(H)$$

From which instead of saying the left sides of these equations are seconds, we say they are proton-seconds by not letting the units of m_p cancel with the bodies of these equations on the left, which are in units of mass, but rather divide into them, giving us a number of protons. I say this is the biological because these are the hydrocarbons the backbones of biological chemistry. We see they display sixfold symmetry. I can generate integer numbers of protons from the time values from these equations for all of the elements with a computer program. Some results are:

```
By what value would you like to increment?: 0.25
How many values would you like to calculate for t in equation? (No more than 100): 100
24.1199 protons 0.250000 second 0.119904 decpart
12.0600 protons 0.500000 second 0.059952 decpart
8.0400 protons 0.750000 second 0.039968 decpart
6.0300 protons 1.000000 second 0.029976 decpart
4.0200 protons 1.500000 second 0.019984 decpart
3.0150 protons 2.000000 second 0.014988 decpart
2.1927 protons 2.750000 second 0.192718 decpart
2.0100 protons 3.000000 second 0.009992 decpart
1.2060 protons 5.000000 second 0.205995 decpart
1.1486 protons 5.250000 second 0.148567 decpart
1.0964 protons 5.500000 second 0.096359 decpart
1.0487 protons 5.750000 second 0.048691 decpart
1.0050 protons 6.000000 second 0.004996 decpart
0.2487 protons 24.250000 second 0.248659 decpart
0.2461 protons 24.500000 second 0.246121 decpart
0.2436 protons 24.750000 second 0.243635 decpart
Program ended with exit code: 0
```

A very interesting thing here is looking at the values generated by the program, the smallest integer value 1 second produces 6 protons (carbon) and the largest integer value 6 seconds produces one proton (hydrogen). Beyond six seconds you have fractional protons, and the rest of the elements heavier than carbon are formed by fractional seconds. These are the hydrocarbons the backbones of biological chemistry. And carbon is the core element of life. We see the duration of the base unit of measuring time, 1 second, given to us by the ancients (the base 60, sexagesimal, system of counting of the Sumerians who invented math and writing and started civilization), is perfect for the mathematical formulation of life chemistry. Here is the code for the program, it finds integer solutions for time values, incremented by the program at the discretion of the user:

```
#include <stdio.h>
#include <math.h>
int main(int argc, const char * argv[]) {

    int n;
    float value=0, increment,t=0, p=1.67262E-27, h=6.62607E-34,G=6.67408E-11,
    c=299792458,protons[100],r=0.833E-15;

    do
    {
        printf("By what value would you like to increment?: ");
        scanf("%f",&increment);
        printf("How many values would you like to calculate for t in equation 1 (no more than 100?): ");
        scanf("%i",&n);
    }
    while (n>=101);
    {
        for (int i=0; i<n;i++)
        {
            protons[i]=((137*137)/(t*p))*sqrt(h*4*(3.14159)*(r*r)/(G*c));

            int intpart=(int)protons[i];
            float decpart=protons[i]-intpart;
            t=t+increment;
            if (decpart<0.25)
            { printf("%.4f protons %f seconds %f decpart \n", protons[i], t-increment, decpart);
              }
            }
        }
    }
```

We have that

$$\frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 18769 \frac{0.833E-15}{1.67262E-27} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi(6.62607E-34)}{(6.67408E-11)(299,792458)}} = 6.029978s \approx 6s$$

Since this 6 seconds is also proton-seconds we have

$$5). \quad \frac{1}{6_{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 1second \text{ is carbon (C)}$$

$$6). \quad \frac{1}{1_{proton}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 6seconds \text{ is hydrogen (H)}$$

Our Theory For Hydrocarbons With all that has been said we are equipped to proceed. We want to consider the radius of a hydrogen atom and the radius of a carbon atom. The radius of a carbon atom given in your periodic table of the elements is often 70 to 76 picometers. The covalent radius of hydrogen is given as 31 picometers. The atomic radius of hydrogen is 53 picometers and the atomic radius of carbon is 67 picometers. We want to consider the atomic radii of both, because the covalent radius, determined by x-ray diffraction for diatomic hydrogen, is the size of two hydrogen atoms joined H₂ divided by two, where it is measured that way, joined, in the laboratory. Carbon is C₂ divided by 2. We are interested in the single carbon and hydrogen atoms, because we want to know what our theory for their six-fold symmetry with one another in their representations in proton-seconds says about the way they combine as the skeletons of life chemistry. We start with the Planck constant, h , which is like flux, a mass (perhaps a number of particles) per second over an area. That is it is kilograms per second over square area:

$$h = 6.62607E - 34 J \cdot s = 6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2$$

We have equations 1 and 2:

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6 \text{ protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1 \text{ second is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1 \text{ proton}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6 \text{ seconds is hydrogen (H)}$$

We can write these

$$\left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{6 \text{ seconds}}{m_p} =$$

$$3). \quad \left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{6 \text{ seconds}}{1.67262E - 27 kg} = 2.37689E - 6 m^2$$

$$\left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{1 \text{ second}}{6 m_p} =$$

$$4). \quad \left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{1 \text{ second}}{6(1.67262E - 27 kg)} = 6.602486E - 8 m^2$$

We have from 3 and 4...

$$5). \quad \frac{\frac{h}{m_p} \cdot \frac{(6 \text{ seconds})}{1}}{\frac{h}{m_p} \cdot \frac{(1 \text{ second})}{6}} = \frac{2.37689E - 6 m^2}{6.602486E - 8 m^2} = 35.9999 \approx 40$$

We find the ratio between the surface areas of the hydrogen and carbon atoms:

$$6). \quad H_{surface} = 4\pi(r_H^2) = 3.52989E - 20m^2$$

$$7). \quad C_{surface} = 4\pi(r_C^2) = 5.64104E - 20m^2$$

$$\frac{4\pi(53pm)^2}{4\pi(67pm)^2} = 0.62575 \approx 0.618... = \phi$$

It is the golden mean. These atomic radii are the radii between the nucleus of the atoms and their valence shell, which is what we want because the valence shell is the outermost electrons responsible for the way the hydrogen and the carbon combine to make hydrocarbons. We will write this

$$8). \quad \frac{r_H^2}{r_C^2} = \phi_{HC}$$

I am guessing the reason we have the golden mean here is that it is the number used for closest packing. But what we really want to do is look at the concept of action, for hydrogen given by six seconds and carbon given by 1 second. We take equations 1 and 2:

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6protons} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1second \text{ is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1proton} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6seconds \text{ is hydrogen (H)}$$

And, we write

$$9). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = r_A$$

Where r_A is the radius of the atom, and t its time values given here by equations 1 and 2. We have for hydrogen

$$10). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(6seconds) = 5.5E - 11m$$

This is actually very close to the radius of a hydrogen which can vary around this depending on how you are looking at it, which we said is given by 5.3E-11m. For carbon we have:

$$11). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec+1sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(7seconds) = 6.44E - 11m$$

And this is actually very close to the radius of a carbon atom which is 6.7E-11m. The thing is if we consider the bond length of the simplest hydrocarbon CH₄, methane, which can be thought of as

$$16). \quad r_H + r_C = 5.3E - 11m + 6.7E - 11m = 1.2E - 11m$$

our, equations give

$$17). \quad r_H + r_C = 5.5E - 11m + 6.44E - 11m = 1.2E - 11m$$

which are the same thing. Thus we have the basis for a theory of everything in that it includes the macro scale, the Earth/Moon/Sun System, because we had:

$$1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

and it includes the radius of the proton which is the radius and mass of a proton and gives 1 second

$$1second = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}}$$

and we have the hydrocarbons the skeleton of the chemistry of life give one second

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6protons} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 1second \text{ is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1proton} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 6seconds \text{ is hydrogen (H)}$$

and because they predict the radii of the carbon and hydrogen atoms at the core of life

$$10). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(6seconds) = 5.5E - 11m$$

$$11). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec+1sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(7seconds) = 6.44E - 11m$$

9.0 Solving The F Class Star We now want see how our theory for the wave solution of our solar system (section 1.0) applies to our theory about F, K, and G stars in terms of being associated with copper-silver civilizations and silver-gold civilizations (Introduction in this paper). We have equation 1.17

$$1.17. \sqrt{3} \frac{M_e}{M_\odot} \cdot \frac{r_e^2}{r_m} = (1second)c$$

Which can be written

$$9.1 \ M_p = \frac{1sec}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot c \cdot M_\star \cdot \frac{r_m}{r_p^2}$$

$$= \frac{1sec}{1.732} (299,792,458)(3.2E30kg) \frac{(6.96265E8m)}{(4E11m)^2} = 2.410E24kg$$

In our theory, outlined in the introduction, we surmised for a 16 month year of the FOV star that the mass of the planet would have to be a little less than the Earth's, about 5E24kg. Thus we see the basis unit of time for our F class star would be different than for ours, which is 1 second. We find it is:

$$(2.410E24)t = 5E24$$

$$t = 2seconds$$

Nicely it is about 2 seconds, or very closely exactly double our 1 second so, we see our system of measuring time may very well have given the second as something Natural in the Universe. With a characteristic time of 2 seconds we have the Planck constant for this spectral class F star system. We have from the following equations

$$1.6 \quad \hbar_\odot = (hC)KE_e$$

$$1.7 \quad hC = 1second$$

$$1.8 \quad C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{GM_p^3}}$$

That,

$$9.2 \quad \hbar_\star = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{GM_p^3}} KE_p = (2sec)KE_p$$

$$KE_p = \frac{1}{2} M_p v_p^2, \quad v_p = \sqrt{\frac{GM_\star}{r_p}} = \sqrt{\frac{(6.674E-11)(3.2E30kg)}{4E11m}} = 23,107m/s$$

$$KE_p = \frac{1}{2} (5E24kg)(23,107m/s)^2 = 1.33483E33J$$

$$9.3 \quad \hbar_{\star} = (2sec)(1.33483E33J) = 2.67E33J \cdot s$$

We have the Planck constant for this F star copper-silver civilization. Now we find the mass of its moon. We use the equation for the ground state of our solar system, equation 2.6:

$$2.6. \quad \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1second$$

We write it for the spectral class F star system

$$9.4 \quad \frac{\hbar_{\star}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 2seconds$$

$$M_m^3 = \frac{\hbar_{\star}^2}{Gc} \frac{1}{2sec} = \frac{(2.67E33)^2}{(6.674E-11)(299,792459)2sec} = 5.6268E22kg$$

Thus the density of this moon is

$$V_m = \frac{4}{3}\pi R_m^3 = \frac{4}{3}\pi(2.060E6m)^3 = 3.66E19m^3$$

$$\rho_m = \frac{5.6268E22kg}{3.66E19m^3} = 1,537.377kg/m^3 = 1.537g/cm^3$$

These are very good, and realistic, results. This is, in fact, the density of Saturn's Moon, Enceladus. Enceladus is considered one of the most promising candidates for life in our Solar System. It has a liquid water ocean beneath its icy crust confirmed by the Cassini spacecraft. The presence of geysers at its South Pole suggest hydrothermal vents at it ocean floor that could provide the energy and chemistry to support life. Cassini detected complex organic molecules in the plumes of water vapor erupting from its surface that could potentially be the building blocks for life. We may be able to sample this material from the subsurface ocean because the plumes eject material into space.

We now present the solution to the Schrödinger wave equation for this copper-silver civilization spectral class F star:

$$9.5 \quad KE_p = \sqrt{3} \frac{R_{\star}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_p^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\star}^2}$$

For this system, the condition of the eclipse gives

$$\frac{R_{\star}}{R_m} = \frac{r_p}{r_m} = 574.5, \text{ where as for ours it is } \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} = \frac{r_e}{r_m} = 400$$

We have

$$KE_p = (1.732)(574.5) \frac{(6.674E-11)^2(5E24kg)^2(5.6268E22kg)^3}{2(2.67E33J \cdot s)^2} = 1.38446E33Joules$$

We had found that $KE_p = 1.33483E33J$. So this is an accuracy of

$$\frac{1.33483E33}{1.38446E33} 100 = 96\%$$

This is good. Let's see what the length of the day of this planet would be (its rotation period). We call upon equation 1.10

$$1.10 \quad 1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

And write

$$9.6 \quad 2seconds = \frac{KE_m}{KE_p}(PlanetDay)$$

$$v_m = \sqrt{\frac{GM_p}{r_m}} = \sqrt{\frac{(6.674E-11)(5E24kg)}{6.96265E8m}} = 692.3m/s$$

$$KE_m = \frac{1}{2}(5.6268E22kg)(692.3m/s)^2 = 1.3484E28J$$

$$PlanetDay = (1second) \frac{KE_p}{KE_m} = 1s \frac{(1.33483E33J)}{(1.3484E28J)} = 98,993.6seconds$$

$$= 27.498hours$$

As we will get into in the next section, the planet day characteristic time is not necessarily the same as the characteristic time. It could be one second here as well. Their day is about 27.5 hours compared to ours which is 24 hours. It is good for astronomy, which would have a 13.75 hour night during its spring and fall, and about 15 hour night during its winter. Since this moon has a month of 6315615 seconds, then that is month of 73 day month. In terms of FOV days that is $(24/25.5)73 \sim 64$ FOV day month, which is 8 squared. If in their ancient times if they formulated a calendar and wanted to break up their month into smaller segments, like we did when we made weeks, their week might be 8 days long. Interestingly (as we have 4 months in our year) that results in 8 times 4 = 32 days, which is about our calendar month for some months. The year of its planet is $(3.44664 yr)(365.25 day/yr) = 1,259$ days. In terms of its own days this is 1,098.76 days. However, in this paper we will not model possible calendars of FOV copper-silver civilizations. Keep in mind, while modeling calendars, you might make some months 28 days long, others 31 days long, introduce leap years, and much more to make things work conveniently with mathematical relationships, like we did.

We will recall in section 4.0 that we equated the lunar formulation with the solar formulation to get a characteristics time of 1 second for our planetary system. We had equation 4.5

$$4.5 \quad 1second = 2r_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

In terms of the FoV star system we should have

$$9.7 \quad 2seconds = 2r_p \frac{v_m}{v_p^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_p^2 M_\star}}$$

We have

$$v_p = \sqrt{\frac{GM_\star}{r_p}} = \sqrt{\frac{(6.674E-11)((3.2E30kg)}{4E11m}} = 23,106.71m/s$$

$$2r_p \frac{v_m}{v_p^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_p^2 M_\star}} = 2(4E11) \frac{692.3m/s}{(23,106.71m/s)^2} \sqrt{\frac{(5.6268E22kg)^3 (1.732)}{(5E24kg)^2 (3.2E30kg)}} = 2.0372seconds \approx 2seconds$$

We see it works great and the characteristic time for the FoV star system is indeed 2 seconds. So the whole system solves nicely in terms of our theory. There is something further to consider here, The period of the planet (It's year) and period of its moon (its's month)...

Periods in Earth Days

$$T_{FOVplanet} = 3.44664years$$

$$T_{FOVmoon} = 6315615 = 73.0974days$$

$$(3.44664days)(365.25days/year) = 1,258.885days \approx 1,259days$$

$$\frac{1,259days}{73.1days} = 17.223moons/year$$

There is some room for play here and we chose the mass of the planet so it was close to 16 new moons per year. The moons per year have to be a little larger than 16 to have 16 new moons per year because the sidereal month is shorter than the lunar month. Thus there should be about 76 days in a lunar month if there are about 73 days in a sidereal month so we have close to 16 new moons per year of the planet. The Earth is close to twelve new moons per year but has 13.3 moons per year. We wanted the relationship between this F star and our G star to be close to 12/16~3/4. We found this works quite well.

Periods in FoV Days

The planet day we found was 27.5 hours is approximately 1.146 days. In FoV days where a day is one rotation for the habitable planet that is for the year

$$\frac{1,259days}{1.146days} = 1,098.6FOVdays/year$$

For the days of in the year of the planet in terms of the FOV planet day. The days for its moon's orbit, its lunar month, are

$$\frac{76days}{1.146days} = 66.31Days$$

Thus for inhabitants of this planet we could say they would see their moon orbit their planet in 66.31 days and they might make this their month. However, each special class has a range of mass for the star that makes it an FOV star, and depending on its peculiarities, and indeed we can adjust that a little and as well the mass of the planet, so we could be seeing that the month for their moon is close to 60 days even, because the month our moon is close to 30 days. Such approximations are good for mathematics, and we have made them for our mathematics by dividing the circle into 360 degrees, which is a good number with which to do as such because it is very divisible by numbers used a lot in formulating Nature. We have 365.5 days in our year, which means the Earth moves through about one degree a day in its orbit about the Sun. We may be talking about a civilization that approximates things according to

$$\frac{1,000days/year}{60days/month} \approx 16moons/year$$

to reconcile base 10 ($10^3 = 1000$) with base 60. Both are good bases for mathematics. Base 16 is actually used a lot in software engineering. We use base 10 in general probably because we have 10 fingers to count on. Ten fingers are natural because with five fingers on each hand, five is a number characteristic of the mathematics of life, its square root is used in obtaining the golden ratio, which has mathematical properties used by life. That is why many animals have five appendages on each hand and foot. Physical things in Nature are more characteristic of 6-fold symmetry, like the points on a snowflake, or the sides on regular hexagons like in honeycombs.

10.0 The Radius of a Planet One of the things we should notice here is that in our theory we have determined everything about G2V and FoV star systems except one thing: the radius of the habitable planet itself. If we had that, there would be a lot more that we could determine that would be of great interest. We may be able to do that. The answer may come from ancient Indian Vedic astrology. To the Hindus, 108 is an important number and, as we talked about in section 6.0, there are in their system of measuring time 108,000 vispalas in a day, where a vispala is their base unit of time equal to 0.4 seconds. How does this help? In India they have noticed that the diameter of the Sun is about 108 times the diameter of the Earth, and, that the average distance from the Sun to the Earth (the Earth orbital radius) is about 108 solar diameters. Is it possible that for F, G, and K stars that the following conclusion holds:

$$\frac{D_{\odot}}{D_e} = \frac{r_e}{D_{\odot}} = 108$$

In other words is it true that,

$$D_e = \frac{D_{\odot}^2}{r_e}$$

Which can be written

$$10.1. \quad R_e = \frac{2R_{\odot}^2}{r_e}$$

We have

$$R_e = 2 \frac{(6.96265E8m)^2}{1.496E11m} = 6,481.082m \approx 6,481km$$

The actual radius of the Earth is $R_e = 6,378km$, so this is an accuracy of about

$$\frac{6,378}{6,481} 100 = 98.4\%$$

Which is pretty good. Thus the radius of the FoV habitable planet is

$$10.2. \quad R_p = 2 \frac{R_{\star}^2}{r_p} = \frac{2(1.18365E9m)^2}{(4E11m)} = 7,005,136.5m \approx 7000km$$

We computed the mass of this habitable planet to be a little less than that of the Earth, to be 5E24kg. Thus, the average density of the planet would be

$$V_p = \frac{4}{3} \pi R_p^3 = \frac{4}{3} \pi (7.005E6m)^3 = 1.4398E21m^3$$

$$\rho_p = \frac{5E24kg}{1.4398E21m^3} = 3.4727kg/m^3 = 3.4727g/cm^3$$

The density of the Earth is 5.51g/cm³. This result for the planet around the FOV star is actually close to the density of Mars, which is 3.93 g/cm³. The planet could be rocky with oceans, it would just have a smaller iron core. Or it could have more water to land than the Earth.

We had found (section 6.0) that the angular momentum of the the earth to the Solar System Planck constant was

$$\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} = 2.5$$

This was related to our time measuring system ultimately given to us by the ancient Sumerians as

$$\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

We can now with the radius of the habitable planet around the FOV star compute its angular momentum. We have

$$L_{planet} = \frac{4}{5}\pi M_p f_p R_p^2 = \frac{4}{5}\pi (5E24kg)(1/(98,993.6s)(7.00E6m)^2 = 6.22E33J \cdot s$$

This gives

$$10.3. \quad \frac{L_{planet}}{\hbar_{\star}} = \frac{6.33E33J \cdot s}{2.67E33J \cdot s} = 2.33$$

This is actually very good, which means the length of our planet day is correct which means our characteristic time of 1.00 seconds is correct. We see We had (section 7.0) that for the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary disc from which our Solar System formed was

$$7.10. \quad P(R) = P_0 \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right) \exp \left[-\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} \right]$$

Which was accurate because the exponent is indeed thought to be 2.5. We have for FOV stars

$$10.4. \quad P(R) = P_0 \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right) \exp \left[-\frac{L_{planet}}{\hbar_{\star}} \right]$$

This works well because while the exact value of the exponent, q, depends on the individual star and disc characteristics, observations suggest FOV stars have a slightly shallower pressure gradient compared to G-type stars that are in fact $p \approx 2.3$ to 2.4. This seems to be consistent with both the observational data (photos of such discs) and theoretical models adjusted for the hotter and more luminous nature of F-type stars.

11.0 Solving The K Class Star While we said F-type stars are characteristic of copper-silver civilizations because they have lower metallicities, this is not always true; it depends on the type of F star. The older F-type stars have lower metallicity than G-type stars because they formed in an environment that was not metal-rich because the environment has not been enriched by previous generations of stars. Younger F-type stars (that formed more recently) formed in an environment where previous stellar generations enriched the environment from which the F-star formed. Also, F-type stars are more luminous meaning they have higher radiation pressure, thus may be blowing the heavier metallic elements further out, perhaps beyond the habitable zone of the planet. In general you can say F-type stars have lower metallicity than G-type stars.

In general, younger G-type stars like our Sun tend to have higher metallicities compared to older stars, because they formed in a part of the galaxy that has undergone more stellar generations enriching the interstellar medium. Also they have lower radiation pressure than F stars, meaning the heavier elements needed to form terrestrial planets have not been so heavily blown out beyond the habitable zone.

Like with F-stars and G stars, younger K stars have higher metallicities than older K stars because they formed after other stars enriched the environment where they formed. Also, the radiation pressure is lower in K-stars than in G stars, meaning perhaps not so much metal got blown out beyond the habitable zone.

It in fact may be that we want to say that the stars of the silver-copper type civilizations are the Population II stars which is to say they are older and did not form from gas clouds enriched by earlier generations of stars, and that the stars of the silver-gold type civilizations are the Population I stars, like our Sun, which is to say they are younger and formed from clouds enriched with heavier metals from previous generations of stars. However we do have to say it may depend on spectral class as well because the hotter F-stars have more radiation pressure and whether they formed from metal-rich environments or not, they may blow more heavier elements out of their habitable zones.

However, there is more to it. K-type stars are generally older than G-type stars, they have longer life-spans, meaning they formed in environments that were less enriched by previous generations of stars, that is to say they are usually Population II stars. Thus, they in general have lower metallicities than G-type stars. F-stars, in general, do have lower metallicities than G-type stars as well, because they are usually older than G-stars. Many F-type stars are part of the thick disc or halo populations in our galaxy the Milky Way. G-type stars are generally found in the thin disc region of our galaxy, which tend to have higher metallicities because they are younger and closer to regions of recent star formation. Thus stars like the Sun, G-type stars, in general do have higher metallicities than F or K stars, even though they are in-between the two in spectral class. So, we were right to make F-type stars copper-silver type civilizations, and G-type stars silver-gold type civilizations because in general this would be true, though there can be exceptions. We suggested G-star civilizations can become more sophisticated than F-star civilizations because they have longer life-spans giving more time for intelligent life to evolve. However, K stars have longer life-spans than G stars, so we suggested they can have more sophisticated life than found around G-stars. However, we did not associate any metals in particular with these stars because we started at F-type stars with copper and silver, went to G-type stars with silver and gold, and after gold in this group of elements there is no suitable metal left to utilize in this approach to the theory, Indeed most F-type stars would have copper-silver type civilizations because they are in general older than G-type stars. So, as we begin to solve K-type stars we will start with them as copper-silver civilizations as in general they have lower metallicities.

However it may be, regardless of the metallicity of the star, if it is more luminous, having more radiation pressure, it may blow more heavier elements out of its habitable zone. However, it may

not, because the habitable zone of a more luminous star is further away from it. How that balances out has to be computed. ChatGpt says that in less luminous stars (like G and K-type stars) the habitable zone is closer in, and radiation pressure is lower, allowing rocky planet formation to occur more easily in the inner system (as opposed to easier formation of gas giants from lighter elements). That, these G and K stars are therefore often prime candidates for finding terrestrial planets in stable habitable zones.

We now begin to solve the K-class star. We know their typical properties. For a KoV star we have in solar mass, solar radii, and solar luminosities:

$$\text{Kov: } 0.88M_{\odot} \quad 0.813R_{\odot} \quad 0.46L_{\odot}$$

Thus, the habitable zone of the KoV star is at

$$r_{\text{habitable}} = \sqrt{0.46L_{\odot}} = 0.678\text{AU} = (0.678\text{AU})(1.496E11\text{m}/\text{AU}) = 1.014288E11\text{m} \approx 1E11\text{m}$$

This is the orbital radius of the planet we are considering, r_p . We have the mass of the star is

$$M_{\star} = (0.88M_{\odot})(1.989E30\text{kg}/M_{\odot}) = 1.75E30\text{kg}$$

$$R_{\text{KOVstar}} = R_{\star} = (0.813)R_{\odot} = (0.813)(6.96265E8\text{m}) = 5.66E8\text{m}$$

$$R_{\star} = \frac{Ag}{Cu} r_{\text{KOVmoon}} = (1.7)r_{\text{KOVmoon}}$$

$$r_{\text{KOVmoon}} = r_m = \frac{5.66E8\text{m}}{1.7} = 3.33E8\text{m}$$

We now want to figure out the characteristic time of this KoV system, and from that, its \dot{n}_{\star} . We call upon equation 9.1 for the the Earth, a G2V system:

$$9.1 \quad M_p = \frac{1\text{sec}}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot c \cdot M_{\star} \cdot \frac{r_m}{r_p^2}$$

11.1

$$M_p = \frac{1\text{sec}}{\sqrt{3}} (299,7092458\text{m/s})(1.75E30\text{kg}) \frac{(3.33E8\text{m})}{(1E11\text{m})^2} = 1.00865E24\text{kg} \approx 1E25\text{kg}$$

We theorize this system has 9 new moons per year because the FoV star we guessed had 16 from Nature's 4x4 array, we know the Earth has about 12 completed new moons per year from Nature's 3x4 array, so we surmise the KOV system is Nature's 3x3=9 array from the cross product in three dimensional space. We have

$$T_{\text{KOVplanet}^2} = \frac{4\pi^2}{GM_{\text{KOVstar}}} r_{\text{KOVplanet}^3}$$

$$\frac{4\pi^2}{GM_{KOVstar}} = \frac{4\pi^2}{(6.674E-11)(1.75E30kg)} = 3.380E-19$$

$$T_{KOVplanet} = \sqrt{(3.380E-19)(1E11m)^3} = 18384776seconds = 212.8 \approx 213days$$

$$= 0.5825784years \approx 0.58years$$

Its planet has year of a little more than one half of an Earth year. Now we find the orbital period of its moon:

$$T_{KOVmoon}^2 = \frac{4\pi^2}{GM_{KOVplanet}} r_{FOVmoon}^3$$

I find if taking the mass of the planet to be a little less than the mass of the Earth — the mass of the earth is $5.972E24kg$ — we get 9 moons per the planet's year. I think this is what we want. I find that value is $5.4E24 kg$.

$$T_{KOVmoon} = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi^2}{(6.674E-11)(5.4E24kg)} (3.33E8m)^3} = 2011204.5sec = 23.2779days$$

$$\frac{T_{KOVplanet}}{T_{KOVmoon}} = \frac{212.8days}{23.278days} = 9.14moons \approx 9moons$$

Returning to equation 11.1, $M_p = 1.0E25kg$ gives for the characteristic time of the KOV system

$$(1.0E25kg)t_c = 5.4E24kg$$

$$11.2. \quad t_c = 0.54seconds$$

Now we can determine \hbar_* , the Planck-type constant for the KOV system. We have the orbital velocity of the planet is

$$v_p = \sqrt{\frac{GM_*}{r_p}} = \sqrt{\frac{(6.674E-11)(1.75E30kg)}{1E11m}} = 34,175.28m/s$$

So, the kinetic energy of the planet is

$$KE_p = \frac{1}{2}(5.4E24kg)(34,175.28m/s)^2 = 3.15E33J$$

So,

$$11.3. \quad \hbar_* = (0.54seconds)(3.15E33J) = 1.7E33J \cdot s$$

Which means the mass of the moon of this planet is

$$\frac{\hbar_{\star}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 0.54 \text{seconds}$$

$$M_m^3 = \frac{(1.7E33)^2}{(6.674E-11)(299,792,458 \text{m/s})(0.54 \text{sec})}$$

$$11.4. \quad M_m = 6.443E22 \text{kg}$$

Thus, the density of this moon is from a perfect eclipse

$$11.5. \quad R_{KOVmoon} = R_{KOVstar} \frac{r_{KOVmoon}}{r_{KOVplanet}} = 5.66E8 \frac{3.33E8 \text{m}}{1E11 \text{m}} = 1.88478E6 \text{m}$$

$$V_m = \frac{4}{3} \pi R_m^3 = \frac{4}{3} \pi (1.88478E6)^3$$

$$11.6. \quad \rho_m = \frac{6.443E22}{2.8E19} = 2.3E3 \text{kg/m}^3 = 2.3 \text{g/cm}^3$$

Thus, the density of the moon orbiting the habitable planet of the KOV star is 2.3g/cm³. This density is closest to the moon Ganymede in our solar system, Jupiter's largest moon and, the largest moon in our solar system, which is even larger than our smallest planet, Mercury. It is the third major moon orbiting Jupiter, that is it is the third largest Galilean satellite. It has a density of 1.936g/cm³. The orbital velocity of this KOV moon is

$$11.7. \quad v_m = \sqrt{\frac{GM_p}{r_m}} = \sqrt{\frac{(6.674E-11)(5.4E24 \text{kg})}{(3.33E8 \text{m})}} = 1040.322 \text{m/s}$$

And, its kinetic energy is, then

$$11.8. \quad KE_m = \frac{1}{2} M_m v_m^2 = \frac{1}{2} (6.443E22 \text{kg})(1040.322 \text{m/s})^2 = 3.4865E28 \text{J}$$

Thus, we would compute the KOV planet's day to be (its rotation period)

$$PlanetDay = (0.54 \text{sec}) \frac{3.15E33}{3.4865E28} = 48788.183 \text{seconds} = 13.55 \text{hours}$$

Which is quite a rapid rotation, nearly twice as quick as the the Earth's rotation, which is about 24 hours. But, as we will see this is not correct, and the the actual value works out quite nice, as well as is the reason for it. But let us first verify that our characteristic time of 0.54 seconds is correct on all fronts according to the theory. We start with equation 9.5, the solution for the Schrödinger wave equation:

$$9.5 \quad KE_p = \sqrt{3} \frac{R_{\star}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_p^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_{\star}^2}$$

The equation for a perfect eclipse is

$$\frac{R_{\star}}{R_m} = \frac{r_p}{r_m}$$

We have for our KoV system

$$\frac{R_{\star}}{R_m} = \frac{5.66E5m}{1.88478E6m} = 300.313$$

$$\frac{r_p}{r_m} = \frac{1E11m}{3.33E8m} = 300.300$$

And we see the eclipse ratio is nearly perfectly 300. For our solar system it is nearly perfectly 400. We have

$$11.9 \quad KE_p = (1.732)(300.3) \frac{(6.674E-11)^2 (5.4E24kg)^2 (6.443E22)^3}{2(1.7E33J \cdot s)^2} = 3.126E33J$$

We found earlier in this section

$$KE_p = \frac{1}{2} Mv^2 = 3.15E33J$$

Thus, that is an accuracy of

$$\frac{3.126E33}{3.15E33} = 99.24 \%$$

We want to verify equations 4.5 and 9.7. For the Earth (G2V star) we have

$$4.5 \quad 1second = 2r_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_{\odot}}}$$

And, for the FoV star system we have

$$9.7 \quad 2seconds = 2r_p \frac{v_m}{v_p^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_p^2 M_{\star}}}$$

Thus we want for the KoV system

$$11.10. \quad 0.54seconds = 2r_p \frac{v_m}{v_p^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_p^2 M_{\star}}}$$

$$2(1E11) \frac{(1040.322m/s)}{(34,175.28m/s)^2} \sqrt{\frac{(6.443E22kg)^3(1.732)}{(5.4E24)^2(1.75E30)}} = 0.53674 \approx 0.54seconds$$

So, it check out correctly. As we will remember, in the protoplanetary disc of a FoV star system the pressure gradient is

$$10.4. \quad P(R) = P_0 \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right) \exp \left[-\frac{L_{planet}}{\hbar_{\star}} \right]$$

$$10.3. \quad \frac{L_{planet}}{\hbar_{\star}} = \frac{6.33E33J \cdot s}{2.67E33J \cdot s} = 2.33$$

Where 2.33 is called p, and this is correct from what we know about protoplanetary discs of these stars. And, for a protoplanetary disc of a star like our Sun

$$7.10 \quad P(R) = P_0 \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right) \exp \left[-\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} \right]$$

$$\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} = \frac{7.05E33}{2.8314E33} = 2.4899 \approx 2.5 = 2\frac{1}{2}$$

Where p=2.5 and this is correct from what we know about protoplanetary discs of these stars. So, let us compute p for our KOV star system from 10.2:

$$10.2 \quad R_p = 2 \frac{R_{\star}^2}{r_p} = 2 \frac{(5.66E8m)^2}{(1E11m)} = 6407120m = 6,407km$$

The KOV planet has a radius about that of our Earth. We have its rotational angular momentum is

$$11.11. \quad L_{planet} = \frac{4}{5} \pi M_p f_p R_p^2 = \frac{4}{5} \pi (5.4E24kg) \frac{1}{48788.183s} (6,407,120)^2 = 1.142E34J \cdot s$$

We have

$$\frac{L_{planet}}{\hbar_{\star}} = \frac{1.142E34}{1.7E33} = 6.7176 = p$$

From observation and data for KOV protoplanetary disc p is about 2.0 to 2.2. We are way off. But as you will remember, we said the rotation of the planet was unusually fast. The interesting thing is as we go from F stars to G stars p increases (2.3 to 2.5) but then when we go from G stars to K stars, it decreases to 2.0. This is because of the the relationship of mass to luminosity of a K star, the relationship for p is not linear (going up with increase in star class) but is sinusoidal (starts down, then goes up, then down, with increase in star class). Further, our equation

$$EarthDay = (1second) \frac{KE_{earth}}{KE_{moon}}$$

Exists independent of the theory. Characteristic times from ground states and all other equations are derived in terms of one another. But this equation is not, it was discovered. And we see here, its characteristic times are not necessarily the same as the characteristic times of the star systems. In fact, for the protoplanetary discs to have the right q in terms of our theory, it has to start up, go down, then back up. Where the characteristic time in the equation was the same as the characteristic time for the FoV star system and close to the same for characteristic time for the Sun, it now has to go back up to be close to the FoV system for the KoV system. That is, that short rotation period for the KoV planet has to go up. We find for the PlanetDay equation the characteristic time is around 1.81 seconds. We have

$$11.12. \quad PlanetDay = (1.8seconds) \frac{KE_{planet}}{KE_{moon}}$$

This gives

$$11.13. \quad PlanetDay = 1.81seconds \frac{3.15E33}{3.4865E28} = 163530.76s = 45.425hours$$

We have

$$11.14. \quad L_{planet} = \frac{4}{5} \pi M_p f_p R_p^2 = \frac{4}{5} \pi (5.4E24kg) \frac{1}{163530.7s} (6,407,120)^2 = 3.4072E33J \cdot s$$

Thus we have

$$11.15. \quad \frac{L_{planet}}{\hbar_{\star}} = \frac{3.4072E33J \cdot s}{1.7E33J \cdot s} = 2.00 = p$$

Which is correct for the pressure gradient of the protoplanetary disc of a KoV star system. For our Sun the characteristic time is 1.00 seconds but for the PlanetDay it is closer to 1.2 seconds. But our Sun is a G2V system, not a GoV system. But if we go down to a GoV system, the characteristic time could become 1.00 seconds, depending on planet mass, radius, mass of star and so forth. Interestingly if we go up from a KoV system to a K2V system, the PlanetDay characteristic time could go up from 1.8 seconds to 2.00 seconds in general. We have FoV stars have a PlanetDay characteristic time of 1.00 seconds but there can be some play in the factors. We might want to calibrate our factors, planet size, mass,...and so forth so that FoV is 1 second, GoV is 1 second, KoV is 2 seconds in the diagrams. That is clear if we look at the following diagrams (next page)...

		Characteristic Time
F0V	0	1.00
G2V	1.2	1.21
K0V	2.0	1.8

12.0 Computer Modeling The Planetary Systems

I wrote a program to model our theory for star systems. Keep in mind Mars is further from the Sun, next planet after the Earth, but it has a day of 24 hours like the Earth Does. That would be a good length of day for intelligent life to develop in. With our program we can model any good data on extrasolar planets the comes in. Here is the program. We run it for several types of star systems.

```
#include <stdio.h>
#include <math.h>

int main(int argc, const char * argv[])
{
    float c=299792458,M_star,M_s,r_planet, M_p,r_moon,L_star, ratio,R_s,R_star,n,
    r_p,T_p,moons,T_m,M_planet, t_c,KE_planet, hbar_star, v_p, M_moon, R_moon,
    KE_p,eclipse, v_m, t_characteristic,R_planet,PlanetDay,KE_moon, seconds, L_planet, p,
    V_p, V_m, rho_p, rho_m;
    printf ("What is the mass of the star in solar masses? ");
    scanf ("%f", &M_s);
    printf ("What is the radius of the star in solar radii? ");
    scanf ("%f", &R_s);
    printf ("What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? ");
    scanf ("%f", &L_star);
    printf ("What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/
Cu=1.6975? ");
    scanf ("%f", &ratio);
    printf ("What is the orbital number of the planet? ");
    scanf ("%f", &n);

    M_star=M_s*(1.989E30);
    R_star=R_s*(6.96265E8);
    r_p=sqrt(L_star);
    r_planet=r_p*(1.496E11);
    r_moon=R_star/ratio;

    M_p=((1/(sqrt(n))*c*M_star*(r_moon/(r_planet*r_planet)))/1E24);

    printf("The habitable zone which is the orbital radius of the planet is: %f m \n",
r_planet);
    printf("The mass of the planet is: %f E24 kg \n", M_p);
    printf("Which is: %f Earth masses \n", M_p/5.972);

    T_p=sqrt((4*3.14159*3.14159*r_planet*r_planet*r_planet)/(6.674E-11*M_star));

    printf("The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: %f years \n", T_p/
31557600);

    printf ("How many moons do you want for the moon's orbital period?\n");
    printf ("For example there are 13.379 moons of our moon per Earth year. \n");
    printf ("This gives 12.38 New Moons is approximately 12 New Moons per year. \n");
    scanf ("%f", &moons);

    T_m=T_p/moons;

    printf ("This gives the orbital period of the moon is %f days. \n", T_m/86400);

    printf ("We will use this value to determine the suggested mass of the planet it
orbits. \n");

    M_planet=(4*3.141*3.141*r_moon*r_moon*r_moon)/(6.674E-11*T_m*T_m);

    printf("The mass of the planet is %f E24 kg \n", M_planet/1E24);
```

```

printf ("Now that we know what the mass the planet should be, we \n");
printf ("multiply the original mass M_p by the characteristic time t_c \n");
printf ("to get the mass of the planet M_planet, to find the characteristic time.
\n");

t_c=M_planet/(M_p*1E24);

printf ("The characteristic time is: %f seconds \n", t_c);

printf ("Now we compute the orbital velocity of the planet. It is: \n");
v_p=sqrt((6.674E-11)*M_star/r_planet);
printf ("%f m/s \n", v_p);
printf ("Mass of planet is %f kg \n", M_planet);
KE_planet=0.5*M_planet*v_p*v_p;
printf ("Its kinetic energy is: \n");
printf ("%f E33 J \n", KE_planet/1E33);
hbar_star=KE_planet*t_c;

printf ("Since we know this and the characteristic time, we have \n");
printf ("the star system Planck constant. It is: \n");

printf ("%f E33 Js \n", hbar_star/1E33);

printf ("Knowing this we can determine the mass of the moon. \n");
M_moon=cbrt(hbar_star)*cbrt(hbar_star)/cbrt(6.674E-11*c*t_c);
printf ("It is: %f E22 kg \n", M_moon/1E22);

printf ("The radius of the moon is given by a perfect eclipse. It is: \n");
R_moon=R_star*(r_moon/r_planet);
printf ("%f E6 m \n", R_moon/1E6);

printf ("We need only verify that our star system Planck constant \n");
printf ("works, by trying it in our KE of the planet solution to the wave
equation. \n");

printf ("R_star over R_moon is: \n");
eclipse=R_star/R_moon;
printf ("%f \n", eclipse);

KE_p=sqrt(n)*eclipse*M_planet*(6.674E-11)*M_planet*(6.674E-11)*(M_moon/
(2*hbar_star))*(M_moon/hbar_star)*(M_moon);

printf ("KE_p is: %f J \n", KE_p/1E33);

printf ("We need to verify that the characteristic time is correct \n");
printf ("from the equation for it from equating solar and lunar solutions. \n");

v_m=sqrt((6.674E-11*M_planet)/r_moon);
printf ("Orbital velocity of moon is: %f m/s \n", v_m);

```

```

    t_characteristic=2*r_planet*(v_m/(v_p*v_p)*sqrt((M_moon/M_planet)*(M_moon/
M_planet)*(M_moon/M_star)*sqrt(n)));

    printf ("The characteristic time is: %f seconds \n", t_characteristic);
    printf ("Now we want to compute the characteristic time for the PlanetDay \n");
    printf ("We need to determine the rotational angular momentum of the planet. \n");
    printf ("And, the planet radius to do this. \n");
    printf ("The planet radius is: \n");
    R_planet=2*(R_star*R_star)/r_planet;
    printf ("%f km \n", R_planet/1000);
    printf ("What is the rotation period, or day, in EarthDays? \n");
    scanf ("%f", &PlanetDay);
    PlanetDay=PlanetDay*86400;
    printf ("PlanetDay is: %f seconds \n", PlanetDay);
    printf ("The PlanetDay characteristic time is: \n");
    KE_moon=0.5*M_moon*v_m*v_m;
    seconds=(KE_moon/KE_planet)*PlanetDay;
    printf ("%f seconds \n", seconds);
    printf ("The planetary angular momentum is: \n");
    L_planet=0.8*3.14159*M_planet*(1/PlanetDay)*R_planet*R_planet;
    printf ("%f E33 Js \n", L_planet/1E33);
    printf ("Thus the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary disc \n");
    printf ("has an exponent of p is: ");
    p=L_planet/hbar_star;
    printf ("p=%f \n", p);
    printf ("All that is left to do is to compute the densities of the planets and the
moons. \n");

    V_p=(1.33333)*(3.14159)*R_planet*R_planet*R_planet;
    V_m=(1.33333)*(3.14159)*R_moon*R_moon*R_moon;

    rho_p=M_planet/V_p;
    rho_m=M_moon/V_m;

    printf ("The density of the planet is: %f g/cm3 \n", rho_p*1000/(100*100*100));
    printf ("The density of the moon is: %f g/cm3 \n", rho_m*1000/(100*100*100));
}

```

We now run the program for our solar system and we find it works well..

G2V System (Our Solar System)

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 1
 What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 1
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 1
 What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975? 1.8
 What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
 The habitable zone, which is the orbital radius of the planet is: 149599993856.000000m
 The mass of the planet is: 5.950231 E24 kg
 Which is: 0.996355 Earth masses
 The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 0.999913 years
 How many moons do you want for the moon's orbital period?
 For example there are 13.379 moons of our moon per Earth year.
 This gives 12.38 New Moons is approximately 12 New Moons per year.
 13.379
 This gives the orbital period of the moon is 27.297884 days.
 We will use this value to determine the suggested mass of the planet it orbits.
 The mass of the planet is 6.152200 E24 kg
 Now that we know what the mass the planet should be, we
 multiply the original mass M_p by the characteristic time t_c
 to get the mass of the planet M_{planet} , to find the characteristic time.
 The characteristic time is: 1.033943 seconds
 Now we compute the orbital velocity of the planet. It is:
 29788.230469 m/s
 Mass of planet is 6152200133217478516932608.000000 kg
 Its kinetic energy is:
 2.729543 E33 J
 Since we know this and the characteristic time, we have
 the star system Planck constant. It is:
 2.822192 E33 Js
 Knowing this we can determine the mass of the moon.
 It is: 7.274836 E22 kg
 The radius of the moon is given by a perfect eclipse. It is:
 1.80030 E6 m
 We need only verify that our star system Planck constant
 works, by trying it in our KE of the planet solution to the wave equation.
 R_{star} over R_{moon} is:
 386.749268
 KE_p is: 2.729543 J
 We need to verify that the characteristic time is correct
 from the equation for it from equating solar and lunar solutions
 Orbital velocity of moon is: 1030.284790 m/s
 The characteristic time is: 1.033943 seconds
 Now we want to compute the characteristic time for the PlanetDay
 We need to determine the rotational angular momentum of the planet.
 And, the planet radius to do this
 The planet radius is:
 6481.083008 km
 What is the rotation period, or day, in EarthDays?
 1
 PlanetDay is: 86400.000000 seconds
 The PlanetDay characteristic time is:
 1.222170 seconds
 The planetary angular momentum is:
 7.517118 E33 Js
 Thus the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary cloud
 has an exponent of p is: $p=2.663574$
 All that is left to do is to compute the densities of the planets and the moons.
 The density of the planet is: 5.395113 g/cm³
 The density of the moon is: 2.976465 g/cm³
 Program ended with exit code: 0

F0V System

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 1.61
 What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 1.7
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 7.24
 What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975? 1.7
 What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
 The habitable zone, which is the orbital radius of the planet is: 402532433920.000000m
 The mass of the planet is: 2.381736 E24 kg
 Which is: 0.398817 Earth masses
 The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 3.478191 years
 How many moons do you want for the moon's orbital period?
 For example there are 13.379 moons of our moon per Earth year.
 This gives 12.38 New Moons is approximately 12 New Moons per year.
 17.223
 This gives the orbital period of the moon is 73.762367 days.
 We will use this value to determine the suggested mass of the planet it orbits.
 The mass of the planet is 4.914012 E24 kg
 Now that we know what the mass the planet should be, we
 multiply the original mass M_p by the characteristic time t_c
 to get the mass of the planet M_{planet} , to find the characteristic time.
 The characteristic time is: 2.063206 seconds
 Now we compute the orbital velocity of the planet. It is:
 23042.150391 m/s
 Mass of planet is 4914012012894422959128576.000000 kg
 Its kinetic energy is:
 1.304525 E33 J
 Since we know this and the characteristic time, we have
 the star system Planck constant. It is:
 2.691503 E33 Js
 Knowing this we can determine the mass of the moon.
 It is: 5.598608 E22 kg
 The radius of the moon is given by a perfect eclipse. It is:
 2.047374 E6 m
 We need only verify that our star system Planck constant
 works, by trying it in our KE of the planet solution to the wave equation.
 R_{star} over R_{moon} is:
 578.131042
 KE_p is: 1.304525 J
 We need to verify that the characteristic time is correct
 from the equation for it from equating solar and lunar solutions
 Orbital velocity of moon is: 686.315674 m/s
 The characteristic time is: 2.063206 seconds
 Now we want to compute the characteristic time for the PlanetDay
 We need to determine the rotational angular momentum of the planet.
 And, the planet radius to do this.
 The planet radius is:
 6961.071777 km
 What is the rotation period, or day, in EarthDays?
 1.146
 PlanetDay is: 99014.406250 seconds
 The PlanetDay characteristic time is:
 1.000793 seconds
 The planetary angular momentum is:
 6.044071 E33 Js
 Thus the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary cloud
 has an exponent of p is: $p=2.245612$
 All that is left to do is to compute the densities of the planets and the moons.
 The density of the planet is: 3.477929 g/cm³
 The density of the moon is: 1.557404 g/cm³
 Program ended with exit code: 0

Now we run it for the K0V star we modeled...

K0V System

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 0.88
 What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 0.813
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 0.46
 What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975? 1.7
 What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
 The habitable zone which is the orbital radius of the planet is: 101463662592.000000m
 The mass of the planet is: 9.798795 E24 kg
 Which is: 1.640789 Earth masses
 The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 0.595374 years
 How many moons do you want for the moon's orbital period?
 For example there are 13.379 moons of our moon per Earth year.
 This gives 12.38 New Moons is approximately 12 New Moons per year.
 9.14
 This gives the orbital period of the moon is 23.792141 days.
 We will use this value to determine the suggested mass of the planet it orbits.
 The mass of the planet is 5.166112 E24 kg
 Now that we know what the mass the planet should be, we
 multiply the original mass M_p by the characteristic time t_c
 to get the mass of the planet M_{planet} , to find the characteristic time.
 The characteristic time is: 0.527219 seconds
 Now we compute the orbital velocity of the planet. It is:
 33930.992188 m/s
 Mass of planet is 5166112134934765332594688.000000 kg
 Its kinetic energy is:
 2.973904 E33 J
 Since we know this and the characteristic time, we have
 the star system Planck constant. It is:
 1.567899 E33 Js
 Knowing this we can determine the mass of the moon.
 It is: 6.153838 E22 kg
 The radius of the moon is given by a perfect eclipse. It is:
 1.857680 E6 m
 We need only verify that our star system Planck constant
 works, by trying it in our KE of the planet solution to the wave equation.
 R_{star} over R_{moon} is:
 304.715332
 KE_p is: 2.973904 J
 We need to verify that the characteristic time is correct
 from the equation for it from equating solar and lunar solutions
 Orbital velocity of moon is: 1017.576111 m/s
 The characteristic time is: 0.527219 seconds
 Now we want to compute the characteristic time for the PlanetDay
 We need to determine the rotational angular momentum of the planet.
 And, the planet radius to do this
 The planet radius is:
 6316.110352 km
 What is the rotation period, or day, in EarthDays?
 1.8927
 PlanetDay is: 163529.281250 seconds
 The PlanetDay characteristic time is:
 1.751937 seconds
 The planetary angular momentum is:
 3.167431 E33 Js
 Thus the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary cloud
 has and exponent of p is: $p=2.020176$
 All that is left to do is to compute the densities of the planets and the moons.
 The density of the planet is: 4.894716 g/cm³
 The density of the moon is: 2.291640 g/cm³
 Program ended with exit code: 0

13.0 Further Modeling Star Systems

KOV System Modeled For PlanetDay Characteristic Time of 2 Seconds

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 0.88
 What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 0.813
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 0.46
 What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975?
 1.7
 What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
 The habitable zone which is the orbital radius of the planet is:
 101463662592.000000 m
 The mass of the planet is: 9.798795 E24 kg
 Which is: 1.640789 Earth masses
 The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 0.595374 years
 How many moons do you want for the moon's orbital period?
 For example there are 13.379 moons of our moon per Earth year.
 This gives 12.38 New Moons is approximately 12 New Moons per year.
 9.6
 This gives the orbital period of the moon is 22.652102 days.
 We will use this value to determine the suggested mass of the planet it
 orbits.
 The mass of the planet is 5.699199 E24 kg
 Now that we know what the mass the planet should be, we
 multiply the original mass M_p by the characteristic time t_c
 to get the mass of the planet M_{planet} , to find the characteristic time.
 The characteristic time is: 0.581622 seconds
 Now we compute the orbital velocity of the planet. It is:
 33930.992188 m/s
 Mass of planet is 5699199403774126933934080.000000 kg
 Its kinetic energy is:
 3.280779 E33 J
 Since we know this and the characteristic time, we have
 the star system Planck constant. It is:
 1.908175 E33 Js
 Knowing this we can determine the mass of the moon.
 It is: 6.788848 E22 kg
 The radius of the moon is given by a perfect eclipse. It is:
 1.857680 E6 m
 We need only verify that our star system Planck constant
 works, by trying it in our KE of the planet solution to the wave equation.
 R_{star} over R_{moon} is:
 304.715332
 KE_p is: 3.280779 J
 We need to verify that the characteristic time is correct
 from the equation for it from equating solar and lunar solutions
 Orbital velocity of moon is: 1068.788818 m/s
 The characteristic time is: 0.581622 seconds
 Now we want to compute the characteristic time for the PlanetDay
 We need to determine the rotational angular momentum of the planet.
 And, the planet radius to do this.
 The planet radius is:
 6316.110352 km
 What is the rotation period, or day, in EarthDays?
 2
 PlanetDay is: 172800.000000 seconds
 The PlanetDay characteristic time is:
 2.042286 seconds

The planetary angular momentum is:
 3.306809 E33 Js
 Thus the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary disc
 has an exponent of p is: $p=1.732969$
 All that is left to do is to compute the densities of the planets and the
 moons.
 The density of the planet is: 5.399798 g/cm³
 The density of the moon is: 2.528113 g/cm³
 Program ended with exit code: 0

Modeling K0V Again (02)

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 0.88
 What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 0.813
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 0.46
 What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975?
 1.7
 What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
 The habitable zone which is the orbital radius of the planet is:
 101463662592.000000 m
 The mass of the planet is: 9.798795 E24 kg
 Which is: 1.640789 Earth masses
 The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 0.595374 years
 How many moons do you want for the moon's orbital period?
 For example there are 13.379 moons of our moon per Earth year.
 This gives 12.38 New Moons is approximately 12 New Moons per year.
 9.8
 This gives the orbital period of the moon is 22.189816 days.
 We will use this value to determine the suggested mass of the planet it
 orbits.
 The mass of the planet is 5.939139 E24 kg
 Now that we know what the mass the planet should be, we
 multiply the original mass M_p by the characteristic time t_c
 to get the mass of the planet M_{planet} , to find the characteristic time.
 The characteristic time is: 0.606109 seconds
 Now we compute the orbital velocity of the planet. It is:
 33930.992188 m/s
 Mass of planet is 5939139086244628588920832.000000 kg
 Its kinetic energy is:
 3.418902 E33 J
 Since we know this and the characteristic time, we have
 the star system Planck constant. It is:
 2.072228 E33 Js
 Knowing this we can determine the mass of the moon.
 It is: 7.074662 E22 kg
 The radius of the moon is given by a perfect eclipse. It is:
 1.857680 E6 m
 We need only verify that our star system Planck constant
 works, by trying it in our KE of the planet solution to the wave equation.
 R_{star} over R_{moon} is:
 304.715332
 KE_p is: 3.418902 J
 We need to verify that the characteristic time is correct
 from the equation for it from equating solar and lunar solutions
 Orbital velocity of moon is: 1091.055176 m/s
 The characteristic time is: 0.606109 seconds
 Now we want to compute the characteristic time for the PlanetDay
 We need to determine the rotational angular momentum of the planet.

And, the planet radius to do this.
 The planet radius is:
 6316.110352 km
 What is the rotation period, or day, in EarthDays?
 1.8
 PlanetDay is: 155520.000000 seconds
 The PlanetDay characteristic time is:
 1.915441 seconds
 The planetary angular momentum is:
 3.828919 E33 Js
 Thus the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary cloud
 has an exponent of p is: $p=1.847731$
 All that is left to do is to compute the densities of the planets and the
 moons.
 The density of the planet is: 5.627133 g/cm³
 The density of the moon is: 2.634548 g/cm³
 Program ended with exit code: 0

Modeling K0V 03

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 0.88
 What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 0.813
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 0.46
 What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975?
 1.7
 What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
 The habitable zone which is the orbital radius of the planet is:
 101463662592.000000 m
 The mass of the planet is: 9.798795 E24 kg
 Which is: 1.640789 Earth masses
 The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 0.595374 years
 How many moons do you want for the moon's orbital period?
 For example there are 13.379 moons of our moon per Earth year.
 This gives 12.38 New Moons is approximately 12 New Moons per year.
 9.8
 This gives the orbital period of the moon is 22.189816 days.
 We will use this value to determine the suggested mass of the planet it
 orbits.
 The mass of the planet is 5.939139 E24 kg
 Now that we know what the mass the planet should be, we
 multiply the original mass M_p by the characteristic time t_c
 to get the mass of the planet M_{planet} , to find the characteristic time.
 The characteristic time is: 0.606109 seconds
 Now we compute the orbital velocity of the planet. It is:
 33930.992188 m/s
 Mass of planet is 5939139086244628588920832.000000 kg
 Its kinetic energy is:
 3.418902 E33 J
 Since we know this and the characteristic time, we have
 the star system Planck constant. It is:
 2.072228 E33 Js
 Knowing this we can determine the mass of the moon.
 It is: 7.074662 E22 kg
 The radius of the moon is given by a perfect eclipse. It is:
 1.857680 E6 m
 We need only verify that our star system Planck constant
 works, by trying it in our KE of the planet solution to the wave equation.
 R_{star} over R_{moon} is:

304.715332
 KE_p is: 3.418902 J
 We need to verify that the characteristic time is correct
 from the equation for it from equating solar and lunar solutions
 Orbital velocity of moon is: 1091.055176 m/s
 The characteristic time is: 0.606109 seconds
 Now we want to compute the characteristic time for the PlanetDay
 We need to determine the rotational angular momentum of the planet.
 And, the planet radius to do this.
 The planet radius is:
 6316.110352 km
 What is the rotation period, or day, in EarthDays?
 1.7
 PlanetDay is: 146880.000000 seconds
 The PlanetDay characteristic time is:
 1.809028 seconds
 The planetary angular momentum is:
 4.054150 E33 Js
 Thus the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary disc
 has an exponent of p is: p=1.956421
 All that is left to do is to compute the densities of the planets and the
 moons.
 The density of the planet is: 5.627133 g/cm³
 The density of the moon is: 2.634548 g/cm³
 Program ended with exit code: 0

Modeling GOV Star System

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 1.06
 What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 1.100
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 1.35
 What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975? 1.8
 What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
 The habitable zone, which is the orbital radius of the planet is: 173819494400.000000
 m
 The mass of the planet is: 5.139235 E24 kg
 Which is: 0.860555 Earth masses
 The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 1.216354 years
 How many moons do you want for the moon's orbital period?
 For example there are 13.379 moons of our moon per Earth year.
 This gives 12.38 New Moons is approximately 12 New Moons per year.
 13.4
 This gives the orbital period of the moon is 33.154713 days.
 We will use this value to determine the suggested mass of the planet it orbits.
 The mass of the planet is 5.551060 E24 kg
 Now that we know what the mass the planet should be, we
 multiply the original mass M_p by the characteristic time t_c
 to get the mass of the planet M_planet, to find the characteristic time.
 The characteristic time is: 1.080134 seconds
 Now we compute the orbital velocity of the planet. It is:
 28452.089844 m/s
 Mass of planet is 5551059943186440862564352.000000 kg
 Its kinetic energy is:
 2.246851 E33 J
 Since we know this and the characteristic time, we have
 the star system Planck constant. It is:
 2.426899 E33 Js
 Knowing this we can determine the mass of the moon.
 It is: 6.483453 E22 kg
 The radius of the moon is given by a perfect eclipse. It is:
 1.874837 E6 m
 We need only verify that our star system Planck constant

works, by trying it in our KE of the planet solution to the wave equation.
 R_star over R_moon is:
 408.510956
 KE_p is: 2.246851 J
 We need to verify that the characteristic time is correct
 from the equation for it from equating solar and lunar solutions
 Orbital velocity of moon is: 933.111816 m/s
 The characteristic time is: 1.080134 seconds
 Now we want to compute the characteristic time for the PlanetDay
 We need to determine the rotational angular momentum of the planet.
 And, the planet radius to do this
 The planet radius is:
 6749.413086 km
 What is the rotation period, or day, in EarthDays?
 1.2
 PlanetDay is: 103680.007812 seconds
 The PlanetDay characteristic time is:
 1.302460 seconds
 The planetary angular momentum is:
 6.129886 E33 Js
 Thus the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary disc
 has an exponent of p is: $p=2.525810$
 All that is left to do is to compute the densities of the planets and the moons.
 The density of the planet is: 4.310134 g/cm³
 The density of the moon is: 2.348706 g/cm³
 Program ended with exit code: 0

P is typically 2.1 to 2.6 for G0V stars where it is 2.0 to 2.5 for G2V stars. We know for our Sun experimentally G2V has p is about 2.5. Our original model for the FoV star system was perfect, it gave a characteristic time of 2.00 seconds and 1.00 seconds for the PlanetDay characteristic time which was exactly what we want for and FoV star because F-type stars is where we might suggest conditions for intelligent life begin in the HR diagram and we want even multiples of 1 second even to extend the naturalness of 1 second in our theory to beyond the proton and our Solar System.

14.0 Modeling Red Dwarf Star Systems

It is currently difficult to detect Earth-sized terrestrial planets around the habitable zones of bright stars like ours, G2V, and is easiest around M-type brown dwarf stars because they are not so bright and as such don't flood-out the planet with light, though we may be able to do as such soon with the James Webb telescope recently put into orbit. Brown dwarfs are the most populous stars in our galaxy, but stars like our Sun are optimal for hosting intelligent life. Planets around red dwarf stars in their habitable zones tend to become tidally locked meaning their rotation slows to their orbital period because the habitable zone is so close-in to the star because they are cooler than our Sun. This means such planets always have the same face towards their star as they orbit it which means it is always day on one side and always night on the other, extreme hot on one side, extreme cold on the other, so they would only be habitable in the twilight region between night and day, which we would think is not optimal for intelligent life to evolve, though they do have longer lives than our Sun, while the Sun has a life longer than the hotter O, B, A, and F stars. The Sun, is in the middle of the HR diagram on the main sequence making it stable and perhaps the most optimal for intelligent life, though K stars are becoming of interest because though between G and M stars, their habitable zone is reasonable and at the same time because they are cooler than our Sun, they burn much longer and perhaps more stable. We might suggest the F stars, just before the G stars in the diagram is where good conditions for intelligent life begin Our first try at a model for such stars worked well because the characteristic time came out to 2.00 seconds even and the PlanetDay characteristic time came out to be 1.00 second even and we have as a suggestion in our theory that the second is a Natural unit that has meaning not just for our Earth-Sun system (the ground state in terms of the Moon is one second) but for the atom's proton which a second describes. We modeled F and K stars from the general theories for their masses, sizes, and luminosities, however we modeled the G2V star from our Sun for which we have perfect observed data. It turns out we have pretty good data for the M brown dwarf star TOI 700 which has a few planets in its habitable zone, one Earth-like, but thought to be a bit larger than the Earth. We will use this data to model the M-type star system and treat it as though it has at least one moon that plays some kind of functional role beneficial for life, though it may be our theories where moons are involved with respect to life may be most functional in the region from A to G to K stars. We will model it as a copper-silver civilization because they would have lower metallicities than stars like our Sun. This star is an M2V star meaning it is two notches cooler than an M0V star. The other good feature, as far as we know, is that the planet is the third planet from the star. Even if there are discovered other planets before it, this number may not change because below a certain mass, smaller planets may not take on an orbital number in the equation.

The TOI 700 Planetary System

Now we turn our attention to the TOI 700 Planetary System...It is an M type (red dwarf) star 101.4 ly from Earth (It is close) and harbors the first Earth sized planet in a habitable zone (There are two) with 4 planets all together in its habitable zone. The star is in the Southern Hemisphere constellation Dorado. Two of the planets are in the optimistic habitable zone (TOI 700 d and e). TOI 700 is about 40% the solar mass, about 40% the solar radius, and 55% the solar temperature. The planets were detected by the Transiting Survey Satellite Object of Interest (TESS).

TOI 700 Star

Spectral Class M	TOI 700
Mass (Solar)	0.416+/-0.010
Radius (Solar)	0.420+/-0.031
Luminosity (Solar)	0.0233+/-0.001
Age	1.5 Gyr

TOI 700 Planets

	TOI 700 b	TOI 700 c	TOI 700 d	TOI 700 e
Mass (Earth)	1.07	7.48	1.72	0.818
Semimajor (AU)	0.0677	0.0929	0.1633	0.1340
Period Earth Days	9.977219	16.051137	37.42396	27.80978
Eccentricity	0.075	0.068	0.042	0.059
Inclination (Deg)	89.60	88.903	89.80	89.60
Radius (Earth)	0.914	2.60	1.073	0.953

We are interested in TOI 700 e. We want to use our program such that it gives the planets mass as

$$M_p = (0.818)(5.972E24kg) = 4.8851E24kg$$

Running The Program

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 0.416
 What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 0.420
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 0.0233
 What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975?
 16.5
 What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
 The habitable zone, which is the orbital radius of the planet is:
 22835447808.000000 m
 The mass of the planet is: 4.867534 E24 kg
 Which is: 0.815059 Earth masses
 The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 0.092455 years
 How many moons do you want for the moon's orbital period?
 For example there are 13.379 moons of our moon per Earth year.
 This gives 12.38 New Moons is approximately 12 New Moons per year.
 45
 This gives the orbital period of the moon is 0.750430 days.
 We will use this value to determine the suggested mass of the planet it
 orbits.
 The mass of the planet is 0.783035 E24 kg

Now that we know what the mass the planet should be, we multiply the original mass M_p by the characteristic time t_c to get the mass of the planet M_{planet} , to find the characteristic time. The characteristic time is: 0.160869 seconds
 Now we compute the orbital velocity of the planet. It is: 49175.910156 m/s
 Mass of planet is 783034814373008953573376.000000 kg
 Its kinetic energy is: 0.946795 E33 J
 Since we know this and the characteristic time, we have the star system Planck constant. It is: 0.152310 E33 Js
 Knowing this we can determine the mass of the moon. It is: 1.931638 E22 kg
 The radius of the moon is given by a perfect eclipse. It is: 0.226963 E6 m
 We need only verify that our star system Planck constant works, by trying it in our KE of the planet solution to the wave equation. R_{star} over R_{moon} is: 1288.456177
 KE_p is: 0.946795 J
 We need to verify that the characteristic time is correct from the equation for it from equating solar and lunar solutions
 Orbital velocity of moon is: 1717.171631 m/s
 The characteristic time is: 0.160869 seconds
 Now we want to compute the characteristic time for the PlanetDay
 We need to determine the rotational angular momentum of the planet. And, the planet radius to do this
 The planet radius is: 7489.764648 km
 What is the rotation period, or day, in EarthDays?
 33
 PlanetDay is: 2851200.000000 seconds
 The PlanetDay characteristic time is: 85.761986 seconds
 The planetary angular momentum is: 0.038719 E33 Js
 Thus the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary cloud has an exponent of p is: $p=0.254215$
 All that is left to do is to compute the densities of the planets and the moons.
 The density of the planet is: 0.444928 g/cm³
 The density of the moon is: 394.435394 g/cm³
 Program ended with exit code: 0

We see the theory falls apart for stars so cool as M-type dwarfs. But then why should we compute according to perfect eclipses in such stars when it seems unlikely you could get intelligent life on their habitable planet, at least as far as we suspect it needs be. In fact they don't need a moon to hold the planet at their tilt like the Earth does to have stable weather, to keep the planet from tilting at 90 degrees then to 180 degrees which could cause temperature extreme swings over short periods of time, because the planet is tidally locked with the star it orbits which could prevent this from happening. M_p in the program works for predicting the mass of the planet, but M_{planet} doesn't involving the characteristic time, but it works with the element ratio around 16 to 16.5. So equation 9.1 works

$$9.1 M_p = \frac{1 \text{ sec}}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot c \cdot M_\star \cdot \frac{r_m}{r_p^2}$$

not adjusting the characteristic time for the second and using the ratio 16.5 in the ratio of the elements. So with no moon, at least that plays a role, we should work out a theory based on equation 9.1 to solve the system for stars of such low masses and temperatures. The ratio 16.5 is what determines the r_m , the orbital radius of the moon, but we don't want to include the moon in a theory for these stars. But in the program $r_{\text{moon}} = R_{\text{star}} / \text{ratio}$ where the ratio here is 16.5. This ratio is much larger than gold to silver (1.8) and silver to copper (1.7). Thus, what determines it? Right off the top of my head this is around oxygen to hydrogen, 16g/mol to 1g/mol. We know our theory predicts hydrocarbons (section 8.0), the skeletons of life chemistry, in the ratio of 1 proton-second to 6 proton-seconds which is carbon, the crux of life, to hydrogen, the most fundamental element. Carbon to hydrogen is 12/1=12 is not far from 16.5. But then our star TOI 700 is a M2V star, maybe carbon to hydrogen is what we need in MOV stars not far from a M2V stars, and M2V is in the ratio of about oxygen to hydrogen.

In the tables for M-class stars the radius of an M2V star is 0.466. TOI 700 is 0.420. Its mass is 0.416. In the tables it is 0.44. But these are averages from surveys, there is some play, because the s-shaped curve in the HR diagram has a thickness. But we want now to consider an MOV star to see how it aligns with carbon/hydrogen=12. The tables give the radius is 0.588, the mass is 0.57, and the luminosity is 0.069 all in solar units. Let's run that section of the program

```

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 0.57
What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 0.588
What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 0.069
What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975?
12.0
What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
The habitable zone, which is the orbital radius of the planet is:
39296704512.000000 m
The mass of the planet is: 4.335389 E24 kg
Which is: 0.725953 Earth masses
The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 0.178304 years

```

We would want to run it for 16 as wells oxygen/hydrogen. We find 12 is better!

```

What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 0.57
What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 0.588
What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 0.069
What is the ratio of element 2 to element 1, ie Au/Ag=1.823, Ag/Cu=1.6975? 16
What is the orbital number of the planet? 3
The habitable zone, which is the orbital radius of the planet is:
39296704512.000000 m
The mass of the planet is: 3.251542 E24 kg
Which is: 0.544464 Earth masses
The orbital period, or year, of the planet is: 0.178304 years

```

We see the year of the planet works as well. We got 0.092455 years for TOI 700 e, is 33.769 days.

What happens is that the star may be small, but the planet is close in giving an absurd eclipse ratio for producing any kind of a reasonable size for the moon resulting in an absurdly high density of it. That is the moon has to be so close to the planet to perfectly eclipse the star, because the star is so close to the planet that it is very large in the sky. Its reduced actual size

doesn't help because it is only about halved. The star is so close to the planet that the orbital period of the planet is only about 30 days, that of our moon around the Earth.

We want to work out a theory where the moon vanishes as a factor stabilizing the planets tilt being replaced by the star playing that role. Perhaps something like the difference between the angular momentum of the planet around the MoV star in the habitable zone minus the angular momentum of our moon around the Earth has to be greater than some critical value. We can already see something like this, in that the orbital period of our moon is about the orbital period the planet around the M star. And indeed we want to reference this with our planet and our sun, because the Sun is midway between the the AoV and KoV stars which define the range over which we are suggesting stars are optimal for intelligent life to take hold and evolve.

Appendix 1

If we want to prove that our planetary Planck constant is correct, the delocalization time for the Earth should be 6 months using it, the time for the Earth to travel the width of its orbit. We want to solve the Schrödinger wave equation for a wave packet and use the most basic thing we can which is a Gaussian distribution. We want to then substitute for Planck's constant h that is used for quanta and atoms our Planck-type constant \hbar_{\odot} (\hbar bar solar) for the Earth/Moon/Sun system then apply it to predict the delocalization time for the Moon in its orbit with the Earth around the Sun.

We consider a Gaussian wave-packet at $t=0$:

$$\psi(x,0) = A e^{-\frac{x^2}{2d^2}}$$

We say that d is the delocalization length and decompose the wave packet with a Fourier transform:

$$\psi(x,0) = A e^{-\frac{x^2}{2d^2}} = \int \frac{dp}{2\pi\hbar} \phi_p e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} p x}$$

ϕ_p is the harmonics of the wave function. We use the identity that gives the integral of a quadratic:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\alpha^2 x + \beta x} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\alpha}} e^{\frac{\beta^2}{4\alpha}}$$

Solve the equation

$$i\hbar \partial_t \psi(x,t) = \frac{\hat{p}}{2m} \psi(x,t)$$

With the initial condition

$$\psi(x,0) = \int dp \cdot e^{\frac{p^2 d^2}{2\hbar^2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} p x}$$

A plane wave is the solution:

$$e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(px - \epsilon(p)t)}$$

$$\text{Where, } \epsilon(p) = \frac{p^2}{2m}$$

The wave-packet evolves with time as

$$\psi(x,t) = \int dp \cdot e^{\frac{p^2 d^2}{2\hbar^2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}(px - \frac{p^2}{2m}t)}$$

Calculate the Gaussian integral of dp

$$\alpha^2 = \frac{d^2}{2\hbar^2} + \frac{it}{2m\hbar} \text{ and } \beta = \frac{ix}{\hbar}$$

The solution is:

$$|\psi|^2 = \exp \left[-\frac{x^2}{d^2} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + t^2/\tau^2} \right] \text{ where } \tau = \frac{md^2}{\hbar}$$

d is the delocalization distance, which for instance could be the width of an atom. τ is the delocalization time, the average time for say an electron to traverse the diameter of the atom and even leave it, to delocalize. If we substitute for \hbar our \hbar_{\odot} , and say that the delocalization distance is for the Moon, the width of the Earth orbit, we should get a half a year for the delocalization time, the time for the Moon and Earth to traverse the diameter of their orbit around the Sun. We have

$$\tau = \frac{m_{moon}(2r_{moon})^2}{\hbar_{\odot}}$$

Where m_{moon} is the mass of the Moon, and r_{moon} is the orbital radius of the Moon. We have

$$\tau = 4 \frac{(7.34767E22kg)(3.844E8m)^2}{2.8314E33J \cdot s} = 15338227 \text{ seconds}$$

Now let's compute a half a year...

$$(1/2)(365.25)(24)(60)(60) = 15778800 \text{ seconds}$$

So we see our delocalization time is very close to the half year over which the Earth and Moon travel from one position to the opposite side of the Sun. The closeness is

$$\frac{15338227}{15778800} 100 = 97.2 \%$$

Thus we know our \hbar_{\odot} is accurate, it continues to function in a theoretical framework. The thing about this is that it means we can predict the mass of the Moon from the Earth year. In terms of what we said earlier that the Moon allows for life by creating the seasons, holding the Earth at its tilt to the Sun, so we don't go through extreme heat and cold, this suggests the Moon has a mass that follows from Earth orbit, which is the habitable zone of the Sun, the right distance for water to exist as liquid, and thus could be as it is for a reason, which means life might be part of a physical process throughout the Universe, that it unfolds naturally in the evolution of star systems.

Appendix 2

Some of the data used in this paper:

$$m_p: 1.67262 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg (Proton Mass)}$$

$$h: 6.62607 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s (Planck Constant)}$$

$$r_p: 0.833 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m (Proton Radius)}$$

$$G: 6.67408 \times 10^{-11} \text{ N} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{kg}^2} \text{ (Gravitational Constant)}$$

$$c : 299,792,458 \text{ m/s (light speed)}$$

$$\alpha : 1/137 \text{ (Fine Structure Constant)}$$

$$q_p = q_e = 1.6022 \text{ E} - 19 \text{ coulombs}$$

$$k_e = 8.988 \text{ E} 9 \frac{\text{Nm}^2}{\text{C}^2}$$

Earth day=(24)(60)(60)=86,400 seconds. Using the Moon's orbital velocity at aphelion, and Earth's orbital velocity at perihelion we have:

$$KE_{moon} = \frac{1}{2}(7.347673 \text{ E} 22 \text{ kg})(966 \text{ m/s})^2 = 3.428 \text{ E} 28 \text{ J}$$

$$KE_{earth} = \frac{1}{2}(5.972 \text{ E} 24 \text{ kg})(30,290 \text{ m/s})^2 = 2.7396 \text{ E} 33 \text{ J}$$

The Author

